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Session B

**PLANT, ANIMAL AND
MICROBIAL
BIOTECHNOLOGY**

**THE BIOMASS QUALITY OF CHIA *SALVIA HISPANICA* L.
AND PROSPECTS FOR ITS USE IN MOLDOVA**

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Chia *Salvia hispanica* Lamiaceae family, also called Mexican chia or salba chia, is an annual herbaceous plant, native to Mexico and Guatemala, where it was an important crop for pre-Columbian Aztecs and other Mesoamerican Indian cultures, characterized by its high nutritional and therapeutically potential. Chia is mainly cultivated as a seed crop. The culinary uses of chia seed have been as a whole seed, seed flour, seed mucilage, and seed oil. *Salvia hispanica* seeds are one of the most-concentrated sources of alpha-linolenic acid (ALA), a plant-based omega-3 fatty acid. Recently interest has been raised on biomass production as a potential forage source opening alleys toward the integration of chia in crop-livestock systems, also as feedstock for renewable energy production.

The objective of this research was to evaluate the quality of green mass from chia *Salvia hispanica* cultivated under the conditions of the Republic of Moldova, and the possibility to use them as fodder for animals and feedstock for biogas production, also the biomass quality of chia dry stalks after harvesting the seeds as feedstock for the production cellulosic ethanol.

We found that the dry matter of the harvested whole plants contained 107 g/kg CP, 80 g/kg ash, 347 g/kg CF, 348 g/kg ADF, 517 g/kg NDF, 65 g/kg ADL, 283 g/kg Cel, 199 g/kg HC, 123 g/kg TSS, with nutritive value 61.79% DMD, RFV= 111, 12.19 MJ/kg DE, 10.1 MJ/kg ME, 6.03 MJ/kg NEI. The nitrogen content in the green mass substrate was 1.71% and estimated content of carbon– 51.1%, the C/N = 29.9 respectively, which played an important role in degradation and biomethane production. The biochemical methane potential of *Salvia hispanica* green mass substrate reached 298 l/kg ODM.

The analysis of lignocellulose composition of chia dry stalks suggested that energy biomass contained 357 g/kg cellulose, 197 g/kg hemicellulose and 72 g/kg acid detergent lignin. The estimated theoretical ethanol yield from cell wall carbohydrates averaged 398 L/t.

Chia *Salvia hispanica* can serve as multi-purpose crops for seed production, alternative forage and feedstock for renewable energy production.

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Key words: *Salvia hispanica* L., fodder, green mass, biomass quality.

THE INFLUENCE OF THE AGRICULTURAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM ON THE SOIL MICROBIOME

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Soil is the fundamental resource of an agricultural ecosystem. Agricultural practices influence the composition of soil bacterial communities. The aim of our work was to study the structure of the soil microbiota in the case of different crop rotation and types of fertilization. The research was carried out in the long-term field experiment on the "Biotron" Experimental Station of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova in two crop rotations (with and without alfalfa). Characterization of the compositional diversity of the soil microbiome was achieved by sequencing amplicons targeting the 16s rDNA gene of prokaryotes (Scientific Center "Genomic Technologies, Proteomics and Cell Biology" of FSBSI ARRIAM, St. Petersburg, Russia).

Anthropogenic soil loading, agricultural management system influenced the formation of soil prokaryote communities. This influence is evident from the analysis of the abundance of *Actinobacteriota* phylum, which in our experiment was second in abundance after Proteobacteria. In the variant *Mineral background* (N45-90P30-60K60-90) was determined the highest abundance of *Actinobacteriota* phylum, being 19.0% in the alfalfa crop rotation and 20.1% in the rotation without alfalfa, respectively. The soil in the forest strip was characterized by the lowest abundance of *Actinobacteriota* filum - 16.0 %. Actinobacteria of the family *Sterptomycetaceae* had the highest relative abundance in the alfalfa rotation, variant *mineral background* (N45-90P30-60K60-90). The forest floor is exposed to less anthropogenic pressure and some oligotrophic-nutrient phyla are more abundant than in agricultural soils. The *Acidobacteriota* phylum had the highest abundance in the forest floor soil - 5.7%. These results can be explained by the fact that *Acidobacteriota* have mostly oligotrophic nutrition strategy with low growth rates and seem to be favoured in resource-limited conditions due to high substrate affinities. The group of microorganisms (clade) *Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium*, which fixes atmospheric nitrogen and promotes plant growth, has the highest share - 1.1 % in the crop rotation without alfalfa, *Organic Fund* variant. The genus *Ensifer*, which includes bacteria capable of inducing root-knot formation in legumes, was detected only in the alfalfa soil with the mineral background variant (N45-90P30-60K60-90). The genus *Streptomyces* (biocontrol agents) had the highest relative abundance (1.3%) in the alfalfa soil with the organic background variant.

Agricultural practices alter the diversity and composition of soil microbial communities, and these altered communities impact the functioning of agricultural ecosystems. Organic fertilization leads to a significant increase in the abundance of some nutrition-related bacteria.

Acknowledgments: The work was carried out in the framework of the project "Efficient use of soil resources and microbial diversity through the application of elements of organic farming" 20.80009.5107.

Keywords: soil microbiome, crop rotation, fertilization, diversity.

DIRECTING THE GROWTH OF CARP LARVAE THROUGH THE APPLICATION OF THERMAL FACTOR

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The study aims to highlight the correlation between environmental parameters (temperature of the aquatic environment) and the consumption of nutrients, in particular, of the yolk sac, as well as the determination of the resistance and growth rate of fish larvae. At the same time, the study was carried out in order to determine the parameters that could be used as a method of increasing the adaptive capacities of animals to the unfavorable action of the environment. The biological material was represented by fish of the species *Cyprinus carpio* subjected to the application of low temperatures in different periods of postnatal ontogenesis. The experiment was performed on two batches of carp larvae aged 1 and 3 days. Each batch of larvae was divided into 3 experimental sublots, in which temperatures of 10 °C, 14 °C and 20 °C were applied. The experiment was carried out in glass vessels with a capacity of 3 liters of water and a density of 500 larvae per liter. The adaptation period to the tested temperatures was 1 hour. The period of application of low temperatures was 1, 3, 5, 7, and 10 days. After the end of the low temperature application period, the carp larvae were transferred to vessels with a water temperature of 20 °C and received abundant food. The studied parameters were monitored at the end of the application periods of low temperatures and additionally at the end after 10 days of feeding the larvae.

The analysis of the obtained data proves that the number of carp larvae aged 1 day, survived after the application of low temperatures is higher than the number of carp larvae aged 3 days and, correspondingly, constitutes 92,83% compared to 80,14%. At a temperature of 20 °C the number of larvae in experimental groups I and II constituted 87,82% and 66,33%, respectively. After 10 days of feeding the larvae, their number in experimental group I is - 83,6%, and in experimental group II - 73,1%.

Further research has focused on determining the influence of environmental factors on the resorption of the yolk sac of carp larvae. Therefore, in the experimental group I the presence of the yolk sac was registered throughout the experimental period (10 days) at application of the low temperature of 10 °C and 14 °C. At the same time, at the temperature of 10 °C the size of the yolk sac at the age of 5 days did not differ significantly from its initial dimensions. In experimental group II, the presence of the yolk sac was registered only at the temperature of 10 °C until the age of 7 days of ontogenesis. At a temperature of 14 °C the yolk sac was practically no longer present at the age of 5 days of the larvae. At the temperature of 20 °C the presence of the yolk sac was registered only up to 3-4 days of application of the thermal factor.

Thus, it can be mentioned that the application of low temperature on carp larvae leads to retention of their development with the keeping of yolk sac for a period of up to 10-12 days after birth. These results are registered at a temperature of 10 °C in the group in which the larvae at the beginning of the experiment were one-day old. Therefore, by applying the thermal factor, it is possible to manage the duration of the development period of carp larvae and to maintain them in case of need for a longer time in the breeding fish farms.

Key words: fish larvae, adaptive capacities, thermal factor.

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF REPRODUCTIVE BIOTECHNOLOGIES IN ANIMAL BIODIVERSITY

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The role and importance of recent biotechnology is constantly growing due to the need to maintain and conservation of biodiversity, as well as increase animal productivity. One of the main biotechnologies of interventions in increasing the improvement of livestock is the continuous improvement of the reproductive properties of the most valuable males, selected from existing livestock based on scientific criteria argued biologically and technologically. Also, the increase of the rhythm of improvement of the herds, foresees the wide application of the reproductive biotechnologies by methods, procedures and operations necessary for the obtaining in optimal conditions, of new generations of animals. The performance of efficient reproductive biotechnologies and their monitoring are imperative for sustainability in any system of breeding and obtaining products of animal origin. Therefore, the existence of obvious challenges for increasing animal productivity in changing environmental conditions can be achieved through conventional breeding biotechnologies. The main effects of the application of reproductive biotechnologies are both in the accelerated improvement of livestock and their health, and in the conditions of reducing the cost price per unit of product. The emergence and use of modern reproductive biotechnologies have opened many avenues for scientific research into the reproductive phenomenon both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. For example, the technology of sex sorting of sperm, which is an advantage in raising animals, to obtain offspring of the desired sex, either male or female. Some biotechnologies also include certain biotechnologies, among which is the induction of estrus and ovulation in physiological off-season, the induction of polioovulation, the synchronization of estrus, the programming of calvings, etc. Animal breeding biotechnologies are currently an area of major importance and performance, a new and promising field of contemporary biology. At the fundamental scientific level with experimental applications, the effects of sperm encapsulation are currently being investigated for a longer preservation of sperm *in vivo*. This biotechnology has been designed to extend the life of sperm at body temperature and to allow the progressive release of viable sperm over several days in various species, including humans. Moreover, biotechnology research is currently being applied on the transcriptomics of the mRNA study at various stages of development, including spermatogenesis; identifying different biomarkers in semen and predicting fertility; biotechnology of intracytoplasmic sperm injection used to treat male infertility, as well as the application of other biotechnologies in various allied fields such as genomics, proteomics, bioinformatics, etc., which are already used in various fields of reproduction, including various animal species. Therefore, there is a need for a clear policy for the correct application and handling of biotechnologies with a multi-institutional approach to solving animal reproduction problems.

Key words: biotechnologie, biodiversity, animal breeding, reproduction problems.

**RESEARCH ON THE INVASIVE IMPACT OF HARMFUL
INSECT COMPLEXES ASSOCIATED WITH PARASITIC NEMATODES
AND PATHOGENIC VIRUS VECTORS IN PRODUCTIVE PLUM
ORCHARDS**

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The cultivation of plum is a centuries-old tradition, surpassed only by apple, and the production of plum fruits obtained in the Republic of Moldova is over 35%, with an important share in exports, about 30%. Plum is such an appreciated crop due to the high productivity of the trees, the special qualities of the fruits and the numerous valuable varieties with diverse fruiting time. The current plum orchards are capital investments, which can be exploited for 20-25 years, and the efficiency of their use depends on the correctness of the establishment of orchards and care techniques in the first 4-5 years after planting.

One of the priorities in the cultivation of plums is the study of the evolution of the parasitic vectorial impact of microbial infections of complexes of harmful organisms, such as associations of harmful insects and invasive nematode complexes in the soil, which also act as vectors of pathogenic viruses, triggering viral infections, which usually occur in pathosystems, triggered by the development of perennial monoculture of plum plantations in time and space. According to the research programs developed based on the project – State Program 2020-2023, we started addressing these strategic objectives in the development of the horticultural sector in the Republic of Moldova, where research on the phytosanitary biological control of invasive and vector insect and nematode communities is conducted annually, to establish the parasitic, functional impact and the structure of associated populations in young and productive plum orchards, breeding nurseries, including other related species such as peach, apricot, cherry etc.

The intensive plum orchards, nurseries for reproducing the planting material from 6 administrative districts, on areas of over 500 hectares, in the North zone (Briceni, Soroca), the Center zone (Criuleni, Nisporeni), the South-East zone (Căuşeni, Ştefan-Vodă) of R. Moldova were investigated. More than 300 samples of soil, young trees, young shoots, young seedlings attacked by viruses were taken from various systems of orchards and breeding nurseries. The soil samples were taken at a depth of 30-60 cm, at intervals of 15-20 days, covering the main phenological stages throughout the growing season. To establish the entomo-helminthiotic and virotic parasitic impact, we performed visual and optical observations to identify local and extensive damage, with symptoms of specific viral infections on trees. The results of the analyzes are interpreted by the values of abundance and frequency of the species (insects on average per 100 leaves, 100 fruits analyzed; nematodes – individuals / 100 cm³ soil), classified by ecological-trophic specialization depending on the age of plantations, environmental conditions, variety, soil, maintenance systems.

As a result of the phytosanitary records carried out during the growing season, in

2020-2022, on the entomo-parasitic impact of the range of invasive insects, a very strong attack was periodically detected, which caused significant losses in fruit production and quality. Their presence in plum orchards is quite difficult to detect, they are often detected too late and spraying insecticides is no longer effective. The damage is usually very extensive; in severe cases the entire plum production is compromised. The most dangerous species detected on plum trees in new type productive orchards are: *Cydia funebrana* – plum fruit moth, *Cydia molesta* – oriental fruit moth, *Hyalopterus pruni* – mealy plum aphid, *Hoplocampa minuta* – black plum sawfly, *Eurytoma schreinerei* – plum seed wasp, species of ectoparasitic aphids and vectors of pathogenic viruses of the genus *Aphis sp.*, *Myzus sp.*, some species of cicadas, mites etc. For this reason, farmers should pay particular attention to spraying insecticides.

The concomitant nematological surveys are also very important, because they also occur as invasive forms and vectors of pathogenic viruses, detected in plantations of various fruit species, including plum. This includes nematode species established as specialized complexes on plum trees, where the most common species that form associations and belong to the orders *Tylenchida* and *Dorylaimida*, the genera: *Pratylenchus*, *Pratylenchus*, *Tylenchus*, *Helicotylenchus*, *Ditylenchus*, *Xiphinema spp.*, *Longidorus*, *Trichodorus*, with endo-ectoparasitic specialization and specialized vectors of various forms of pathogenic viruses, which can trigger specific viral infections in fruit plantations. According to the bibliographic review and the results obtained by us, currently the presence of 15 species of nematodes with invasive impact and vectors of pathogenic viruses specific to plums have been identified. They are represented by associations of the order *Dorylaimida*, the genera *Xiphinema* and *Longidorus*, the species: *Xiphinema index*, *X. vuitennezi*, *X. riversi*, *X. brevicolle*, *X. diversicaudatum*, *Longidorus elongatus*, responsible for the transmission of 20 species of pathogenic viruses and viral infections in plum orchards, detected in practically all areas and sectors investigated.

The investigations carried out in the intensive plum orchards have also highlighted the more advanced etiological composition of 3 viral diseases (ring pattern virus, fan-leaf virus, plum pox virus), detected immediately after the formation of vegetative organs (first growing season), infested and through the numerous insect species with sting-sucking buccal apparatus, such as: aphids, cicadas, mites, wasps, which are associated with complexes of vector nematodes in the soil, especially in the sectors that were previously planted with classic orchards, frequently detected in all zones and growing seasons.

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Key words: plum orchard, harmful insect, parasitic vector, nematode, viral diseases.

VIABILITY OF STREPTOMYCES STRAINS AND ITS VARIANTS AFTER FREEZE-DRYING IN CNMN

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There are currently more than 20 types of strain preservation methods, which can be divided into four categories: subculturing, drying, freeze-drying, and cryopreservation.

All modern methods of preservation and long-term storage of microorganism collection cultures are based on the transfer of cells to an anabiotic state with an appropriate partial state (storage on medium with minimal necessity of nutrients, in sterile vessels, under a layer of mineral oil, in distilled water, at low temperatures, etc.) or complete (drying, freeze-drying, cryopreservation, etc.) cessation of metabolism. Each of the methods has its own advantages and disadvantages and can have a different effect not only on the viability, but also on the preservation of the characteristic properties and physiological, biochemical, and genetic features of the culture. In connection with the need to develop integrated approaches to the conservation of microorganisms, it is important to note that the practice of conservation, which has developed over many decades, has empirically developed a number of examples which, to one degree or another, correspond to those mechanisms. Immersion of cells of microorganisms in an anabiotic state which have been identified (and continue to be detected) in the study of the formation, properties and germination of specialized resting cells of microorganisms.

Thus, freeze-drying of microbial strains is one of the most sustainable methods, but it requires the greatest manpower, special equipment and trained personnel. Thus, the purpose of the research was to evaluate the viability of *Streptomyces* strains maintained in the National Collection of Non-Pathogenic Microorganisms (CNMN) after freeze-drying to determine the effectiveness of the method.

The basic strains and their variants served as objects of study: *Streptomyces levoris* (CNMN-Ac-01, CNMN-Ac-15, CNMN-Ac-16); *S. mauvecolor* (CNMN-Ac-12, CNMN-Ac-17, CNMN-Ac-18); *S. gougerotii* (CNMN-Ac-14, CNMN-Ac-19, CNMN-Ac-20). For the long-term preservation of lyophilized *Streptomyces* strains, protective medium gelatin 2.5 % + glucose 7.5 % was used. The contents of the vials with sporulating material was frozen at -50°C. Freeze-drying taken place for 8 hours, at the Labconco 6 plus freeze-drying machine at a pressure of 6-7 Pa and a temperature of -94°C. The determination of the viable germ load by inoculation on solid culture media, the cells that cause colony formation are called colony forming units and their number is approximately equal to the number of microbial cells in the sample. According to results the viability of all 9 strains after freeze-drying varying between 88.7 – 97.8 %. Freeze-drying was successful, because the viability of the strains was higher than 85.0 %.

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Key words: microbial strains, viability, conservation method, freeze-drying method.

SPECIFIC STREPTOCOCCI OF THE DIGESTIVE TRACT AND THEIR SUITABILITY FOR INCLUSION IN PROBIOTIC PREPARATIONS

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It is now known that normal intestinal bacteriocenosis consists of bacilli and cocci. The elaboration of probiotic biopreparations, intended to reconstitute its deregulated composition, is mainly carried out with the use of bacteria in the form of bacilli, and of cocci - very limited (only *Enterococcus faecium* species).

The aim of the present work was to study the background of intestinal streptococci in healthy children of various ages and to argue their use in the development of microbial composition of new probiotic biopreparations.

The investigations were carried out in several steps. The first was devoted to the isolation of streptococci currently existing in the healthy intestinal contents; the second - to their identification and the third - to the calculation of the percentage share of various genera of intestinal streptococci specific to children of various ages. As a result, 834 streptococcal monotypic isolates were isolated and assigned to three genera of the *Streptococcaceae* family. The percentage share was higher in streptococci specific to children aged 1-3 years (genus *Lactococcus*), constituting 46.31-46.98%. In second place were those of the genus *Streptococcus* (31.57-37.73 %) and third - *Enterococcus* (18.66-22.10 %). In children aged 5-16 years, there was a predominance of enterococci (38.18-46.77 %), a sharp decrease in lactococci (28.18-13.70 %) and a relative maintenance of those of the genus *Streptococcus* (33.92-39.51 %).

Thus, in healthy children of various ages it was found:

- the incidence of some intestinal representatives of the family *Streptococcaceae*;
- their genus membership and the percentage share of streptococci of the genera useful to the body.

It was demonstrated the opportunity of recommendation and differentiated use of streptococci from the studied genera in case of elaboration of new composition of probiotic biopreparations, intended for children of 1-3 years (genus *Lactococcus*), 5-16 years - (*Enterococcus*) and 1-16 years - (*Streptococcus*).

Key words: intestinal streptococci, children, biopreparat, probiotic effect.

**NEW DATA ON LADYBUGS (INSECTA) FROM THE
REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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Ladybugs (Insecta: *Coccinellidae*) are beneficial, predatory insects that enjoy increased attention from researchers due to their high potential as biological control agents in organic agriculture. Despite its small size, ladybugs consume a large number of plant pests such as aphids, thrips, mites, scale, whitefly populations etc.

The first study of ladybugs species diversity from the Republic of Moldova was performed, after which 48 species from 28 genera and 7 tribes belonging to the family Coccinellidae were identified. Among the most common species native for the Republic of Moldova are *Adalia bipunctata*, *Coccinella septempunctata*, *C. undecimpunctata*, *Coccinula quatuordecimpustulata*, *Hippodamia variegata*, *Tytthaspis sedecimpunctata* and invasive *Harmonia axyridis*.

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Key words: insect, biological control agent, diversity, Republic of Moldova.

**INITIATION OF THE *IN VITRO* CULTURE OF THE
MACROCARPON VACCINIUM AITON VARIETY 'EARLY BLACK'**

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The research was carried out in the Laboratory of Embryology and Biotechnology of the National Botanical Garden (Institute) "Alexandru Ciubotaru". Cranberry (*Vaccinium macrocarpon* Aiton), is a shrub about 20-30 cm tall, with red fruits (1-2 cm in diameter), evergreen leaves and white or pale pink flowers. Fruits have multiple health benefits, an increased content of protein, vitamins A, B1, B2, C, minerals, tannins, fiber, flavonoids, saponins, phenols and essential fatty acids Omega 3, 6 and 9, oils and sugars, are energizing, helps eliminate stress, anxiety and depression. Based on the nutritional and therapeutic importance of cranberries, research has been initiated on obtaining seedlings by in vitro multiplication. During the research, several sterilization procedures were developed. According to the literature for the inoculation of *Vaccinium* species is used plant material consisting of shoots fragments containing apical buds or nodal fragments, harvested from mature plants.

The explants were taken from the donor plants in June, during the active vegetation period of the plants. Fragments of shoots with apical buds were taken for inoculation. The biological material was brought to the laboratory, where it was fragmented and washed under cold water. After washing with detergent solution, the fragments were placed in KMnO₄ solution (about 3%) to which 2.3 drops of Tween were added for 10 min. The biological material was then transferred to the box, rinsed 4 times with sterile distilled water (autoclaved) and sterilized. For this species we used 3 sterilization regimens: 1) the plant material was sterilized with a solution of mercuric chloride (ethanol mercury chloride) 0.1% for 5 minutes; 2) the plant material was aseptitized with 0.05% chlorhexidine solution for 5 minutes; 3) the plant material was sterilized with 0.25% lysoformin solution for 10 minutes. This was followed by rinsing with sterile distilled water, then placing the biological material in 3% H₂O₂ solution (for 1 min.) And repeated rinsing with sterile distilled water. After this process, the biological material was fragmented under the laminar and inoculated into test tubes (one inoculum in the test tube) on agarized nutrient medium: WPM - 100%, zeatin - 0.5 mg / l, sucrose - 30 g / l, agar - 5 g / l, pH - 5.0.

Following the research, we established that exposure to these sterilization reagents did not cause necrotization of the explants, however the most beneficial method of asepsis for the given culture is with mercury chloride of 0.1% (5 minutes), the process of infestation of explants being less than 50%. After sterilization with a chlorhexidine solution of 0.05%, about 30% of viable inoculums were obtained, with a solution of lysoformin of 0.25% - about 10%.

Acknowledgments: The research was carried out within the project: 20.80009.19 "Introduction and elaboration of technologies for multiplication and cultivation by conventional techniques and in vitro cultures of new woody plant species".

Key words: *Vaccinium macrocarpon*, variety, in vitro multiplication.

**INFLUENCE OF SOME COORDINATION COMPOUNDS WITH
POLYDENTATE LIGANDS ON THE PROTEOLYTIC ACTIVITY OF
FUSARIUM GIBBOSUM CNMN FD 12**

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In order to increase the enzymatic activity of mycelial fungi the influence of some new coordination compounds of Ba, Sr and Ca, including as a ligand dimethyl ester of 2,6-pyridinedicarboxylic acid, on the activity of acid (pH-3.6), neutral (pH-7.4) and alkaline (pH-9.0) proteases synthesized by the mycelial fungal strain *Fusarium gibbosum* CNMN FD 12 was studied. The compounds were added to the nutritive medium in concentrations of 5, 10 and 15 mg/L. The enzymatic activity was determined in dynamics on the 4-6th days of cultivation, period of maximum accumulation of proteases. The effect of the tested compounds on the enzymatic activity varied significantly depending on the composition and concentration of the compound, as well as the duration of cultivation and the type of enzymes. It was found that the compound of barium in concentrations of 5 and 10 mg/L intensified the biosynthesis of enzymes, ensuring on the 4th day of cultivation high levels of alkaline proteases, comparable to the maximum value presented by the control (without coordination compounds) on 5th day of cultivation. Thus, the activity of alkaline proteases on the 4th day of cultivation was by 25.7 and 35.8% higher compared to the control from the same day and by 6.2 and 14.7% - compared to the maximum value of control (5th day). The metalocomplex of Sr showed a pronounced inhibitory effect on the accumulation of acid proteases in all experimental variants and an increase in alkaline protease activity by 44.2-83.7%. Calcium containing compound exerted a moderate positive effect on acid proteases, in all tested concentrations, ensuring the increase of activity by 13.7-15.8%. In the same time, in concentrations of 15 mg/L, it increased the activity of alkaline proteases by 11.6% and extended the period of active synthesis of neutral proteases, the activity significantly exceeding (by 307.3%) the level of the control of the same day and being practically similar with the maximal value of control.

The evaluated compounds exerted a significant distinct influence, from negative to neutral and positive, on the biosynthesis of the enzymatic components of the proteolytic complex synthesized by the micromycete *Fusarium gibbosum* CNMN FD 12 and can be used for obtaining of enzymatic preparations with different, programmed composition, depending on the field of application.

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Keywords: *Fusarium gibbosum*, ligand, coordination compounds of Ba, Sr and Ca, proteases synthesis.

MEANS OF ENHANCING THE ROLE OF BIOLOGICAL NITROGEN IN PHYTOTECHNY

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According to several sources, biological nitrogen plays an important role in the growth, development and productivity of agricultural plants. The share of biological nitrogen in their harvest is about 20%. The rest of the nitrogen comes from mineral fertilizers (30%), organic (8%), seeds (7%) and soil (35%). It is also known that with increasing doses of mineral fertilizers their effectiveness decreases, in agricultural production increases the accumulation of nitrates, intensifies their migration into the environment (water, soil, air, etc.). One of the alternative sources of supplemental plant in nutrition with nitrogen is atmospheric nitrogen fixed microbially. The intensification of the use of molecular nitrogen can be performed in several ways such as: increasing the areas of the crops of leguminous plants, bringing them in the structure of crops up to 20-25%. For this it is necessary to ensure the optimal conditions for the symbiotic fixation process (optimization of aeration and water regime, introduction of the required amount of phosphorus fertilizers and necessary micro-fertilizers).

The use of microbial preparations based on nitrogen-fixing symbiotrophic bacteria, usually significantly increases the symbiotic potential, positively influences the harvest and accumulation of crude protein. The effectiveness of inoculants can be considerably increased by creating "super-effective" *Rhizobium* strains (using the methods of molecular biology and genetics), which would combine all the qualities (activity, ecological plasticity, technology, competitive ability, etc.).

When developing new varieties and hybrids of leguminous plants, it is necessary to assess the "symbiosis" in order to select plant forms that have an increased potential for fixing biological nitrogen. If in the years 1960-1990 soybean varieties and hybrids were created which in symbiosis with the nodule bacteria after its harvest in the soil accumulate from 60 to 90 kg / ha of biological nitrogen, then after the 90s of last century, with the development molecular biology varieties and hybrids with an increased potential for molecular nitrogen accumulation in the atmosphere of 300-500 kg / ha were developed.

In the Republic of Moldova, strains of soybean nodule bacteria with high biological nitrogen fixation capacities were selected, based on which the *Rizolic* biopreparation was obtained, which is currently used for seed treatment before sowing. The research carried out on the lots of the Experimental Base of the ASM, of the Field Crops Research Institute "Selectia" and on the testing field of agricultural crops belonging to the Ministry of Agriculture and Food Industry (s. Bacioi) showed that bacterialization of seeds is an important element in soybean plant cultivation.

Following several years of research, the following conclusion was reached: the use of nodular bacteria of *Rhizobium japonicum* RD2 in soybean culture promotes plant growth, development and productivity while stimulating the nitrogen-fixing activity of the rhizobio-root system.

Key words: microbial preparation, biological nitrogen, agricultural production.

THE USE OF MICROBIAL BIOPREPARATIONS IN MODERN BIOTECHNOLOGIES

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The creation of new local biopreparations that are the basis of local bacterial, capable of presenting that are of perspective, than than their use with imported properties, which are of interest and practical for the country. Mixed microbial biopreparations are created from strains of agronomic microorganisms and their improvement aims to direct the processes that occur in the soil with scientific and practical applications.

Preparations obtained with microorganisms and biologically active substances that differ especially when applied on microorganisms and biologically active substances under conditions of combination with different ecological-physiological bacteria that differ especially in their application on different agro-climatic zones in the composition of preparations with several components can be created from symbiotic associative and rhizosphere microorganisms. Biopreparations create with a complex action, at the same time complex action, at the same time taking into account the properties to decide many problems of biological protection of plants and increase the amount of production (vegetable, fruit, herbs, animal feed), but also improvement.

Most often the bacterial preparations are created to increase the productivity of agricultural plant, that are used microorganisms to the following families, species classes, *Rheziobiaceae*, as well as the genera *Azotobacter*, *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Agrobacterium*, *Azospirillum*, Such, non-harmful organic preparations that are created on the basis of microorganisms isolated from natural objects (agricultural plants).

Concurrent microorganisms are of major importance, as the spermosphere (phyloplane) of plants, contribute to the correlations of plants, which move up the complicated ecological pattern for plants of plants from the necessary microorganisms, harmful and neutral. In the rhizosphere area with bacteria, actinomycetes, fungi, algae, nematodes. In the rhizosphere we find many negative bacteriogram of these bacteria) that protect plants from phytopathogens, which stimulate growth and increase plant productivity. Except with free azotrophs and in associations, species (*Azotobacter*, *Bacillus*, *Klebsiellas*, *Azospirillum*) play an important role in the association and in nitrogen-fixing symbiotic communities, partly in the formation of nodules of berry plants with the combined use of several *Rhizobium* and *Bradrhizobium* strains. The second, third and fourth components of microbial preparations, which contain bacteria, rhizobacteria, mycorrhizal fungi, as well as biologically active substances have a practical importance have a practical importance in their use in modern biotechnologies.

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Key words: biopreparat, microorganism, active substance.

BIODETERIATION OF PLASTIC MATERIALS BY PHYTOREMEDIATING MICROORGANISMS

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In the Republic of Moldova and in the EU countries we have a dense pollution of the environment with plastics, including polyethylene, include low density polyethylene (LDPE). Plastic under the action of microorganisms biodegrade into smaller particles, which hit the soil, water and air, reflecting a negative impact on the soil environment plant growth and productivity. The lower the biodegradation of plastic by plants leads to negative consequences on food security and the development of sustainable agriculture. Biodegradation refers more to the impact of microorganisms on the safety of plastic properties, without the chemical transformation of carbon-containing compounds into plastic and biodegradability for these processes must take time. Microbial communities resistant to various adverse conditions can have many unique characteristics.

Among a number of properties of soil microorganisms in different climatic zones, with different capacities to decompose plastic, it is worth mentioning more and more. Adaptation to new carbon sources can create new characteristics of microorganisms, especially those that produce active enzymes. Adaptive enzymes to adverse conditions of microorganisms that offer you insights into a new wide range of applied problems, such as non-recyclable plastic pollution. Synthetic plastics present in everyday materials are the main anthropogenic residues, which enter with polluting environment. The reform, changes in the ecosystem caused by anthropogenic influences such as plastic pollution can have an aromatic impact on a global scale.

Although the issue of plastics remains unresolved, different podules are considered to reduce their impact on the environment. One of them is to use microorganisms capable of biodegrading plastic. Thus, the potential of microorganisms from various unfavorable conditions can be used in outdoor air landfills. Among the prominent microbial agents used for biodegradation, belonging to the following species *Pseudomonas*, *Streptomyces*, *Corynebacterium*, *Asthrobacter*, *Micrococcus*, *Adreia*, *Leifsonia*, *Cryobacterium* and *Flavobacterium*, *Colvella*, *Marimonas* and *Shewwanela*. In laboratory conditions vegetative experiments were carried out with the aim of applying photostimulating microorganisms with non-recyclable polyethylene biodegradation capabilities to the development and growth of *P. sativum* plants. The results were carried out experimentally and can be used for the purpose of stimulating, growing peas and forming the rhizobioradicular system in soil conditions contaminated with LDPE. The strain was applied as a study object. *Rhizobium leguminosarum sp1*. In some variants in the present study process (LDPE) inhibition of growth and development was observed. Phenomenon saturation of the plant during growth and development, being due to the presence of small polyethylene particles leading to sudden major toxicity. Bacteria seeding with *Rizobium.leguminasatum sp 1*. was manifested with respect to the matrix with all the characteristics of the plant are increased significantly by 16,8% in the dry mass of the plant, and in the variants with film compared to the control, being 11.8%. The presence in the soil of plastic in the form of polyethylene (LDPE) by way of biodegradation suddenly leads to inhibition of the growth of *P. sativum* plants and the formation of the rhizobio radicular system until their loss.

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Key words: pollution, biodegradation capabilities, microbial agents.

STUDY OF THE SYNERGISM BETWEEN MICROBIOLOGICAL AGENTS IN CONTROL OF APPLE SCAR

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The apple during the vegetation is attacked by a wide complex of pathogens that lead to enormous losses of fruit, both in quantity and quality. Among the most dangerous, widespread and common diseases of the apple are: apple scar (*Venturia inaequalis*), powdery mildew (*Podosphaera leucotricha*), brown rot (*Monilinia fructigena*), fire blight (*Erwinia amylovora*), and bacterial canker (*Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *syringae*).

The purpose of this study – evaluation of the synergism between microbiological agents *Pseudomonas fluorescens* AP-33 (trade name Rizoplan) and *Trichoderma lignorum* M-10 (trade name Trichodermin-SC) in control of the apple scar (*Venturia inaequalis* Wint). The experiments were mounted in the field in apple in 8 variants /3 repetitions/3 trees per repetition, according to approved methods. In the variant Standard was used chemical fungicide Jeck –Pot, EC (Difenoconazole+Penconazole 200+100 g/l). The biological efficacy in the control of apple scar in the result of the foliar application have been evaluated as followed: Rizoplan 2,0 l/ha - 72.3%; Trichodermin SC 2,0 l/ha - 76.6%; Rizoplan + Trichodermin SC 2.0 l/ha- 74.5%; Rizoplan 3.0 l/ha - 78.7%; Trichodermin SC 3,0 l / ha - 80.9% and combine application of the Rizoplan + Trichodermin SC 3,0 l / ha - 81.9%. The intensity of the disease development was maximum in the Control variant (4.7%) and minimum in the Standard variant 0.7%. In the variant Standard (Jeck –Pot, EC) with an application rate of 0.4 l/ha the biological efficiency reached 85.1%. The biological efficacy in fruits also depended on the application rate: variant Rizoplan 2.0 l/ha - 77.2%; Trichodermin SC 2,0 l / ha -78.6%; in the variant Rizoplan + Trichodermin SC 2.0 l/ha - 82.8%; Rizoplan 3.0 l/ha - 77.9% and Trichodermin SC 3.0 l/ha -79.3%; in the variant Rizoplan + Trichodermin SC 3,0 l / ha-84.1%, the best efficacy. The biological efficacy against apple scar in the Chemical standard (Jeck –Pot, EC) with an application rate of 0.4 l/ha was 80.7%. In can be concluded that the application rate of 3.0 l/ha of the mixture Rizoplan + Trichodermin SC have demonstrated the highest efficacy in the control of apple scar: 81.9% - on leaves and 84.1% - on fruits.

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Key words: apple scar, synergism, Rizoplan, Trichodermin-SC, diseases of the apple.

ANTIOXIDATIVE PROTECTION IN THE BIOTECHNOLOGY OF AGRICULTURAL BREEDING

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Negative external and internal biotechnological and biological factors cause decreased welfare and stress of birds, and their adaptation is due to the integrity of exogenous and endogenous antioxidant mechanisms under stress. For example, temperature, noise, light, transport and chemical effects, consumption of stimulants, food change, technological, biotechnological, experimental and hierarchical factors in the herd. In the conditions of industrial poultry farming, the adaptation of birds is possible through the use of antioxidants and other components of the ration. Therefore, a balanced diet with a set of important nutrients can be considered as one of the main elements for the successful control of stressors in birds. The main factor in combating stress is the antioxidant system of the bird's body. The latter is diverse, responsible for protecting cells from the action of free radicals and includes multiple components - natural fat-soluble antioxidants, water-soluble antioxidants, antioxidant enzymes, the thioredoxin system and other. The structural components of protective antioxidants are located in cellular organs, in subcellular or extracellular space. The functionality of these structures of the living cell antioxidant system provides the three main protection mechanisms. First, the formation of free radicals is prevented by removing their precursors with antioxidant enzymes, SOD, glutathione, GSH-Px and metal binding proteins.

The second mechanism - is achieved by the properties of vitamin E, ubiquinol, carotenoids, vitamin A, ascorbic acid, uric acid and other antioxidants. The third mechanism of protection occurs through the functionality of lipases, peptidases or proteases and other enzymes, which systemically eliminate and repair damaged molecules. Therefore, the scientific community proposes the concept of antioxidant protection of cells, which consists in the fact that the protection activated by the received antioxidants is based on preventing the release of free electrons in cellular mitochondria by purifying the original radicals. Therefore, in the final stage, metal ions are bound to their binding proteins and transformed into non-toxic substances. In parallel with exogenous antioxidants, endogenous mechanisms take place in the body of birds, mainly of enzymatic origin of antioxidant protection.

These enzymatic complexes metabolize free radicals in the presence of important micronutrient cofactors, including selenium, iron, manganese, copper and zinc. Simultaneously with maintaining the metabolism in the body of birds during the growing period, antioxidants also influence the oxidation of lipids in meat after slaughter during storage and in eggs, thus helping to maintain the health of products and human health. At the same time, the use of antioxidants remains of scientific importance for further agro-ecological research in the field of agricultural production, which provides for the welfare of the environment during the further development of animal biotechnologies in the agro-industrial complex.

Key words: adaptation of birds, protective antioxidants, agricultural breeding, biological factors, biotechnology.

**TAXUS BACCATA L.-MORPHO-STRUCTURAL CHARACTERS
IN SPONTANEOUS AND CULTIVATED TAXA**

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Taxus baccata L. is a conifer species with a special economic status. This study aims to present the micro-morphological and histo-anatomical changes of the leaf apparatus in the genus *Taxus* L. taxa, spontaneous and cultivated in Romania.

The biological material analyzed was represented by leaves collected from yew individuals belonging to the spontaneous species *Taxus baccata* L. (Yew Reserve - Tudora Forest, Botoșani County) and from two taxa: *T. baccata* `Robusta` and *T. baccata*, cultivated (S.C. Doropad S.R.L. Suceava). The cross-sections and double coloration (iodine green and ruthenium red) were made according to the methodology of the Vegetal Anatomy Laboratory of the "Al. I. Cuza" University.

All species show the following characteristics: in the vicinity of the stomatal band can be observed a band of regular radially elongated epidermal cells, arranged in 10-11 rows, approximately rectangular, narrow outline, with numerous papillary protuberances, in contrast to the remaining approximately 10-12 bands towards the edge of the leaf blade, with rectangular cells, covered by a fine, smooth cuticle, covering the straight outer walls, devoid of papillary protuberances. With the following difference: in the taxa *T. baccata* spontaneous and *T. baccata* `Robusta` this band of papilliform epidermal cells is absent, its characteristics being very similar to those of the midrib.

The histo-anatomical analysis of the leaf revealed the following aspects: the leaf is hypostomatous, with stomata arranged in bands in variable numbers per band, on either side of the vein, and, as a peculiarity, it does not present lignified sclerenchyma hypodermis; the resin canals are absent; the tracheid parenchyma is poorly represented and is mainly seen on the lateral side of the conducting fascicle, in the form of small expansions which exceed the limits imposed by the perfectly superimposed phloem tissue over the woody tissue; the crenulated appearance of the cuticle is because it molds onto the protuberances of the outer walls of the lower epidermal cells (papillary cells).

The micro-morphological and histo-anatomical investigations carried out on the leaves of the studied taxa are in general agreement with the literature for the spontaneous *T. baccata* (Goodman et al., 2001).

Key words: *Taxus baccata* L., *T. baccata* `Robusta`, micro-morphological analysis, histo-anatomical investigations.

**THE ROLE OF *PELOPHYLAX RIDIBUNDUS* (PALLAS, 1771)
IN THE FORMATION AND MAINTENANCE
OF PARASITIC ZOONOSES**

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Amphibians as definitive, intermediate, complimentary and reservoir hosts, for various species of parasites, are "vector" organisms which, being obligatory in the development of parasites, constitute the favorable environment for the penetration, development and conservation of evolutionary forms of parasitic agents.

Amphibians are a category of biological vectors that, moving from the aquatic environment to the terrestrial one, ensure development and multiplication, at least for one biological stage, which gives them the role of source of a pathogen and, at the same time, transmits a variety of parasitic forms. They have a special role in the contamination of areas favorable to certain parasites and participate directly in the formation of parasitic zoonoses.

The role of amphibians in formation and maintenance of the zoonosis, it started when it was amplified by the direct human contact with animals and has expanded with the introduction of domestication of different vertebrate animals.

According to the helminthological investigations performed on *Pelophylax ridibundus* species, amphibians from Ranidae family, in the center and southern area of the Republic of Moldova, the presence of 19 helminths species was established: *Haematoloechus variegatus* Rudolphi, 1819; *Codonocephalus urniger* Rudolphi, 1819; *Opisthioglyphe ranae* Froelich, 1791; *Paralepoderma brumpti* Buttner, 1951; *Prosotocus confusus* Looss, 1894; *Tylodelphys excavata* Rudolphi, 1803; *Diplodiscus subclavatus* Pallas, 1760; *Parastrigea robusta* Szidat, 1928, *Strigea falconis* Szidat, 1928; *Gorgodera varsoviensis* Sinitzin, 1905; *Haplometra cylindracea* Zeder, 1800; *Pleurogenoides medians* Olsson, 1876, *Cosmocerca ornata* Dujardin, 1845; *Oswaldocruzia filiformis* Goeze, 1782; *Icosiella neglecta* Diesing, 1851; *Spirocerca lupi* Rudolphi, 1809; *Toxocara canis* Werner, 1782; *T. leonina* Linstow, 1902 and *Acanthocephalus ranae* Schrank, 1788, which from a taxonomic point of view fall into 3 classes, 7 orders, 17 families and 18 genera.

According to our helminthological investigations performed on amphibians from the families *Ranidae* and *Bufonidae*, we are established their role as hosts for two species of helminths *Toxocara canis* and *T. leonina* with an impact on the health, in the foreground, of humans and animals (cats, dogs).

Infestation of amphibians with the nematode species *Spirocerca lupi* Rudolphi, 1809 is another proof of their role as vectors, but also their participation in the formation and maintenance of parasitic zoonoses. The species *Spirocerca lupi* causes spirocercosis - one of the parasitic diseases of both domestic and wild vertebrates, it was spread all over the world. This species of nematode forms spirocercosis in carnivores (dog, fox, wolf), and accidentally in goats, horses, cattle, pigs, etc., it is located in the esophagus, clinically characterized by digestive, cardiovascular and general disorders. By detecting the trematode species *Codonocephalus urniger* Rudolphi, 1819 - a trematode with trixene life

cycle, the role of amphibians as "biological vectors" is also asserted, because various species of birds such as: *Botaurus stellaris* Linnaeus, 1758, *Ixobrychus minutus* Linnaeus, 1766, *Ardea purpurea* Linnaeus, 1766, *Egretta garzetta* Linnaeus and other, are the definitive hosts. *Parastrigea robusta* Szidat, 1928, from the Strigeidae family is another species of trematode, that was detected in amphibians in the muscles and less often on the mesentery. The larval form of this species (metacercarie) is also found in fish: *Abramis brama*, *Atherina mochon pontica*, *Alburnus alburnus* and other. The adult forms are parasitic in the intestines of herons and of day predators, especially of the Ardeiformes order - *Ardea cinerea*, *A. purpurea*. The infection of birds with trematode of *Parastrigea robusta* species, this is causes parastrigeosis.

The *Strigea falconis* Szidat, 1928 is a trematode species similar to family Strigeidae that was found in amphibians under the muscular fascias around the neck, chest, legs, under the serosa of the esophagus and goiter, in the connective tissue between the trachea and esophagus, under the skin of the neck, chest and legs. Adult forms parasitize in the bird intestines of different orders: Falconiformes, less often Strigiformes and accidentally Passeriformes (*Oriolus melanocephalus*), Galliformes (*Meleagris gallopavo*), Gharadriiformes (*Charadrius dubius*) and Columbiformes (*Streptopelia chinensis*) causing Strigeosis. The larval forms of meso- and metacercariae are found in birds of the Ardeiformes, Columbiformes, Ralliformes, Steganopodes, Anseriformes, Charadriiformes, Lariformes, Falconiformes, Coraciiformes, Galliformes, Strigiformes, Piciformes, Passeriformes orders, as well in amphibians *R. lessonae* species.

Based on the above, the *Pelophylax ridibundus* species, represent of vertebrates species with an amphibiont lifestyle that directly participates in the formation and maintenance of outbreaks of parasitic agents specific to fish, birds, mammals and humans. Therefore, out of the 19 helminths species detected as a result of laboratory helminthological investigations, all species have faunal importance, bioindicators and contribute to solving the problems regarding the zoogeographic reasoning, of which, 6 species are of medical-veterinary importance, through which is affirm the role of amphibians as vectors of various groups of parasites specific too other groups of animals, both domestic, wild, pets and humans

From the above, in the Republic of Moldova, these results for the first time to demonstrate that the amphibian host may be a vector of parasitic agents and suggests that we should begin to consider the role of amphibians in the dissemination and control of some parasitic agents. This aspect be particularly important in coming years, as warmer temperatures are known to increase feeding of amphibians rates, which means that expected warming from climate change may exacerbate the potential role of amphibians as vectors.

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Key words: amphibians, biological vectors, parasitic zoonoses, helminthological investi.

ASEPTICIZATION OF PLANT MATERIAL OF SOME SPECIES OF FAM. AMARYLLIDACEAE L.

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The family *Amaryllidaceae* L. is represented by herbaceous perennials, bulbous or rhizomatous plants, belonging to the Order *Asparagales*, monocotyledons.

Snowdrops are plants that naturally occur in temperate areas of Europe, growing in shady areas, on neutral or slightly acidic soils. In the wild flora, snowdrops grow in deciduous forests, in thickets, in glades and wet and shady grasslands, on plains, on hills and mountains.

In vitro plant propagation by tissue culture is an alternative method of regeneration of rare and endangered species, because in such a case the plant material is usually limited. Sampling small amounts of tissue (explant) from plants does not harm *in situ* populations.

In initiating tissue culture of plant species of the Fam. *Amaryllidaceae* L., an important step is the asepticization of the plant material. The techniques differ from one crop to another, and are carried out depending on the characteristics of the plant. Usually, the plants collected from open ground are more infested as compared with those grown in protected environment. The preliminary care of stored plants can reduce the amount of pathogens in explants. The treatment of plants with fungicidal or bactericidal agents is a good option, but it is sometimes not effective when taking bulb tissue under natural conditions.

The research was conducted according to the basic protocol with some optimizations for rare plant species of Fam. *Amaryllidaceae* L. (*Sternbergia colchiciflora* Waldst. & Kit., *Galanthus nivalis* L., *Galanthus plicatus* Bieb., *Leucojum aestivum* L.), concerning the sterilization regime and obtaining the plant material in order to introduce and micropropagate them by tissue culture.

Thus, four sterilizing agents were tested: calcium hypochlorite, ethyl alcohol, mercury chloride and sodium hypochlorite. The best results were obtained after the use of mercury chloride, with a seedling viability rate of 60% in *Galanthus nivalis* L. and *Galanthus plicatus* Bieb., 70% in *Leucojum aestivum* L. and 85% in *Sternbergia colchiciflora* Waldst. & Kit.

The other sterilizing agents proved to be ineffective, since fungal and bacterial infections were detected in most inoculated explants.

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Key words: family *Amaryllidaceae* L., asepticization of the plant material, rare plant species, sterilizing agents, pathogens in explants.

CONDITIONALLY PATHOGENIC AGENTS OF THE FAMILY ENTEROBACTERIACEAE CAUSING ACUTE DIARRHEA DISEASES

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Acute diarrheal diseases are caused by microorganisms from the family Enterobacteriaceae, which are very numerous and diverse according to their biological characteristics. The family Enterobacteriaceae brings together about 30 genera with over 100 species, which inhabit the intestines of humans and animals, being spread with feces everywhere in the environment. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and UNICEF, there are approximately 2 billion cases of diarrhea each year worldwide, and 1.9 million children under the age of 5 die from BDA, mostly in developing countries.

The studies were conducted during the years 2017-2021. Clinical samples (fecal masses) were collected from patients and investigated in the microbiological laboratory of the MTA Buiucani Public Health Medical Institution of Chisinau. The bacteriological analysis was based on obtaining the pure culture of the pathogen and its subsequent study. A total of 3752 samples were investigated. The identification was made according to the types of colonies. The Enterobacteriaceae family forms S, M or R type colonies, developed on complex culture media of general utility (usual, with native proteins) and special (selective, biochemical tests). *Klebsiella* forms large colonies (up to 4-5 mm), mucoid, with a tendency to converge. *Proteus* forms invasive cultures that spread in the form of concentric waves. *Serratia marcescens* produces red pigment. *Escherichia coli* produces burgundy pink colonies, indole positive on UTI Agar chromogenic medium.

Following the investigations carried out within the group of intestinal bacteria, pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic Enterobacteriaceae species were identified. Conditionally pathogenic enterobacteriaceae are *Klebsiella*, *Proteus*, *Citrobacter*, *Edwardsiella*, *Enterobacter*, *Escherichia*, *Hafnia*, *Morganella*, *Serratia*, *Proteus*, *Providencia* etc. and can cause food poisoning, diarrheal disease, suppurative or septicemic nosocomial (hospital) infections with endotoxin shock. Analyzing the quantitative indices for conditionally pathogenic Enterobacteriaceae during the study period, we find that acute diarrheal diseases were more frequently caused by *Klebsiella* (6.0% - 12.9%), *Enterobacter* (1.2% - 5.8%), *Citrobacter* 0.8% - 2.7%), and *E. coli hemolytica* (1.5% - 3.4%). Quantitative indices of conditionally pathogenic representatives of the family Enterobacteriaceae varies from year to year, the highest incidence being registered in 2020 in *Klebsiella* and *E. coli hemolytica*, in 2018 in *Enterobacter* and in 2021 in *Citrobacter*. The variation in morbidity caused by conditionally pathogenic Enterobacteriaceae is due to living conditions, food and water quality and sanitary regime.

Acknowledgments: The research was conducted within the doctoral project "Pathogens of acute diarrheal diseases - morpho-cultural features, methods of identification, antibiotic resistance and the dynamics of spread in Chisinau city."

Key words: acute diarrheal diseases, conditionally pathogenic enterobacteriaceae, types of colonies, morbidity.

INFLUENCE OF EXTERNAL FACTORS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF *S. SPINOSA* ON THE LIQUID MEDIUM

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Spinosad is a natural insecticide derived from a species of actinomycete bacterium, *Saccharopolyspora spinosa* (Mertz and Yao 1990), which shows the effectiveness of a synthetic insecticide. It consists of the two most active metabolites, called spinosyn A and D. spinosyns, new macrolides, are natural metabolites produced under aerial fermentation by the actinomycete *Saccharopolyspora spinosa*. These compounds contain a unique system of tetracyclic rings to which two different sugars are attached. These features make spinosad a tool for integrated pest management. The discovery and characterization of *S. spinosa* is a new opportunity a progressive insect management tools in natural products. To obtain these metabolites it is necessary to cultivate in large quantities on liquid media. After the research was initiated, the optimization of the solid nutrient medium was performed in order to maintain the culture, when a uniform development of *S. spinosa* colonies was obtained and a sporulation at 7-10 days, the study of in-depth cultivation on liquid media was studied. Then followed the research of the literature to determine the starting points for the development of the liquid culture medium, several key components were determined. According to literature data, most media had an initial pH of 6.8 when inoculated, the growth was very good and even *S. spinosa* has a good production of spinosad. At the first tests, a very weak growth was determined and the mycelium was not even formed. Likewise, when inoculating samples of cultural liquid on solid media to determine CFU, growth was almost absent and solitary colonies were rarely reported. That is why we went on the path of pH adjustment to weak basic, which led to a rapid and very good growth of *S. spinosa*. After the first negative attempts the cultivation time was also optimized from four days was increased to seven days. Little progress was made in cultivation, but they were insignificant. The cultivation temperature was maintained at 28-30 °C, which allows a good development of the culture on agarized media. After several failed attempts, the idea appeared that maybe the initial amount of inoculum is insufficient and the culture simply fails to develop, in order to verify this hypothesis, the use of the mother culture was used. To obtain this, a 750 ml flask was taken and inoculated with spore suspension, cultured for four days, then the cultural liquid was used as culture. When using this process, a uniform growth was obtained in all repetitions of the same compositions of the environment and also the growth begins very quickly. For an industrial use of *S. spinosa* it is also necessary to study each factor separately but with a higher affinity and to experiment with the composition of the environment to obtain a high productivity and a low price of both the environment and those generated by the process. cultivation.

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Key words: *Saccharopolyspora spinosa*, active metabolites, pest management, actinomycete, spinosad.

PROTEOMICS ANALYSIS OF NICOTINE METABOLISM REGULATION IN PAENARTHROBACTER NICOTINOVORANS

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Paenarthrobacter nicotinovorans is a soil Gram-positive nicotine-degrading microorganism (NDM) that harbors a 165 kb pAO1 catabolic megaplasmid. The nicotine catabolic genes on pAO1 have been sequenced, but not all the details on the regulation and interplay of this pathway with the general metabolism of the cell are available. Also, little is known on how the cells cope with the accumulation and toxicity of the resulting nicotine metabolic by-products.

Here, we used nanoLC–MS/MS and performed a time-based proteomic study of *P. nicotinovorans* grown in the presence or absence of nicotine. *P. nicotinovorans* cultures were grown in the presence and in the absence of nicotine. Samples were taken every hour for the determination of bacterial growth (OD at 660 nm), accumulation of the characteristic nicotine-blue pigment (OD at 585 nm) and nicotine levels (by HPLC). Cells were harvested at 3 different time intervals: 7-, 10- and 24-hours after inoculation and washed twice for the removal of nicotine-related metabolites. The cells were lysed, separated on 9–16% SDS-PAGE maxi gels, in-gel digested using trypsin, and the resulting peptides mixture was analyzed by nanoLC-MS/MS using a NanoAcquity UPLC (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) coupled to a Q-TOF Xevo G2 MS (Waters). Data analysis was performed using Mascot v.2.5.1 and Scaffold v.4.8.2).

The approach allowed us to identify a total of 915 proteins grouped in 528 non-redundant protein clusters. We found an extensive number of proteins that are both plasmidal- and chromosomal-encoded which allows us to relate the observed differences in protein abundance to the accumulation of known nicotine intermediates and metabolites. A number of five new chromosome encoded enzymes related to the general metabolism of the cell have been found to be regulated by nicotine and provide an anaplerotic pathway that links the Krebs cycle to the nicotine catabolism in this bacterium. Our time-course proteomics experiments also allow us to determine the when the Krebs cycle is active and when the nicotine pathway becomes active and when the two of them work together for an efficient energetic metabolism via expression of various proteins through chromosomal-plasmidial gene regulation. The mass spectrometry-based proteomics data has been deposited to PRIDE with the dataset identifier PXD012577.

Data provides insights into cells adaptation to nicotine metabolic intermediates and is useful for future attempts to genetically-engineer the strain.

Key words: *Paenarthrobacter nicotinovorans*, proteomic study, nicotine metabolic by-products, chromosome encoded enzymes.

**ATHERINA (*ATHERINA BOYERI* RISSO, 1810)
FROM THE KUCHURGAN RESERVOIR**

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The Kuchurgan reservoir is a reservoir subject to high anthropogenic pressure. This is due to the construction and commissioning of a thermal power plant - Moldavskaya GRES. Before the construction of the power plant and the transformation of the natural estuary into a reservoir - the cooler of the MGRES, the same species of fish were found in it as in the reservoirs of the Lower Dniester. On the territory of Moldova, this is the only body of water that is fundamentally different from other aquatic ecosystems in the region, mainly by a moderate degree of thermofication and increased mineralization - about 2500 mg/l.

Atherina appeared in the Kuchurgan reservoir-cooler of the Moldavskaya GRES in the early 1990s. Atherina got into the reservoir, most likely together with the pumped water from the river. Turunchuk. Due to the high potential of reproduction, as well as eurybiontism, sinter in a short time took a dominant position in terms of numbers in the ichthyocenosis of the Kuchurgan reservoir. Due to the high mineralization and increased thermofication of the reservoir, atherina has found a favorable ecological niche for itself here. Due to the fact that the mineralization of the water in the reservoir is lower than that of the sea, as well as competitive trophic relations with native species, the smelt has formed a local herd with slowed down, almost 2 times compared to the sea, growth, earlier puberty and shortened, almost two times, life cycle. According to the results of control catches in 2019-2022. atherine is the absolute dominant in abundance in the ichthyocenosis of the reservoir.

Currently, it is the most massive species of fish in the reservoir. According to the dominance index, it belongs to the D5 category, according to the constancy index - C2 and C3, according to the environmental significance index - to the W5 category. The maximum dimensions and weight of males are 9.4 cm and 3.9 g, and females are 9.8 cm and 4.3 g, which is lower in comparison with the marine form.

In the Kuchurgan Reservoir, the atherina migrates en masse twice to the coastal part of the reservoir - in spring from early March to early April and in autumn from early October to early November. Being heat-loving, in the autumn-winter periods it migrates to the warm channels of the Moldavskaya GRES, forming large accumulations, which is associated with a higher temperature in comparison with the open water area of the reservoir by about 5 degrees or more. Due to the high concentration of atherine in the warm channels in the autumn-winter period, the number of predators increases here, in particular, asp, which actively feeds on atherine. In addition to predators, carp also feeds on smelt, so in early spring, anglers use smelt as bait and catch carps of impressive size (about 10 kg).

Acknowledgments: Research was carried out within the framework of the project № 20.80009.7007.06 AQUABIO

Key words: atherina, aquatic ecosystems, ichthyocenosis, number of predators, potential of reproduction, eurybiontism.

**PRESENCE OF THE SPECIES *GLAREOLA PRATINCOLA*
(CHARADRIIFORMES, GLAREOLIDAE) IN THE
LOWER PRUT AREA**

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The wetland of Lower Prut is an attractive sector for an impressive 228 species of wild birds. On May 22, 2022 in the arranged fish ponds in the northern part of Lake Manta (Crihana Veche village, Cahul district) 6 specimens belonging to the species were reported *Glareola Pratincola* (Linnaeus, 1766). Collared Pratincole is a rare species in the avifauna of our country, which prefers arid areas, exposed to the sun, sandy, with little vegetation, near the waters. In Romania it is a summer guest, a nesting species. In the Republic of Moldova, it was encountered during migration, the last report being mentioned by ornithologists on September 9, 2000 near Lake Cuciurgan. Some 19th century authors claimed that in the autumn months huge flocks landed in the lower meadows of the Dniester and Prut. Continuous habitat degradation has significantly reduced the species' numbers.

The first 4 specimens encountered this year were observed on the dry strip in the vicinity of the water, where the grassy carpet was made up of small plants of *Rumex acetosa* and fragments of dried stems of *Oenanthe aquatica*. At our appearance two specimens flew, two more remained on the ground, fluttering, spreading and swelling its wings. Near the birds were 5 specimens of *Charadrius dubius* who were looking for food at the water's edge. Our attention was drawn by the behavior of the specimens of *Recurvirostra avosetta* and *Himantopus himantopus*, who were flying and making shrill sounds in flight, as if wanting to attack. The specimens left on the ground mimicked that they were injured. They defended the colony located in the poor vegetation where nests could be seen consisting of 3-4 eggs. We also met 2 pairs of *Piet avocet* that accompanied their chicks through the small water. At about 50-60 m from the colony, through the grassy carpet about 8 cm high, we came across 2 mature specimens of *Collared Pratincole*. And in this case the birds were agitated, attracting attention by the movements made on the ground or by the sounds made in flight. This kind of behavior is practiced by birds during the breeding season, when adult birds want to take the predator away from the nesting site. Most likely the nests could be hidden in the higher grass zone in the middle of the field. Presence during the summer of the species *Glareola pratincola* and birds behavior involves nesting the species in the Manta Lake ecosystem.

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Key words: *Glareola pratincola*, avifauna, colony of wild birds, nesting the species, rare species.

THE INFLUENCE OF CLASSICAL BIOTECHNOLOGIES ON THE WELFARE OF AGRICULTURAL BIRDS

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Modern biotechnology, representing the interference of biological and technological performance, currently practically occupies the most privileged position in the practice of the poultry sector. At the same time, biotechnology is the use of the concepts of engineering and biological sciences to produce goods from biologically derived materials, for example food in industrial poultry farming. By applying biotechnologies in current poultry farming, real, technologically feasible performances are obtained and the prospects of an increased yield in industrial poultry farming are created, with decisive economic and social effects for the near future. The main advantages of obtaining meat and eggs in biotechnological conditions are their properties to improve animal and human health, maintaining biodiversity and balancing the environment. Poultry biotechnology aims to change the biological properties of the body of birds and increase their productivity. Moreover, current biotechnology evaluates through scientific research according to market development trends, market size perspective, potential opportunities, market share by types of poultry biotechnology and practical production applications. In addition, increasing the health and productivity of birds and increasing research and development in poultry biotechnology are the main drivers of this agricultural sector. Raising awareness of basic and applied research on bird welfare and the implementation of advanced biotechnologies is one of the factors in the future development of the poultry sector. Recent advances in molecular biology, immunology and genetic engineering have multilaterally expanded the scope of study and use of biotechnology in agricultural poultry in industrial growth conditions. Poultry meat and eggs are sources of high quality protein and amino acids, minerals, lipids and fatty acids, vitamins, carbohydrates and other bioactive components. There is also a special specialized field of scientific research on the use of whole products obtained through biotechnologies, especially in poultry feed. The future of biotechnology is to use the principles of increasing the development of birds and their health, increasing reproduction and improving nutritional quality, as well as the safety of poultry products. Currently poultry farming is continuously improved through a variety of biotechnological technologies.

Advances in biotechnology are evolving rapidly, scientific achievements in poultry genome sequencing, technological advances in molecular markers and other applications of biotechnology will provide new research opportunities to improve and modernize the poultry breeding and exploitation industry. In the future, it is expected that the genetic composition of birds will be available, allowing the selection of the most suitable agricultural birds for a given production framework. If the genetic information of a bird population is sufficiently diverse, it is more likely to adapt successfully to environmental changes.

Keywords: modern biotechnology, poultry farming, health and productivity of birds, market development trends.

**REFERINȚE ASUPRA CONDIȚIILOR GEOGRAFICE ȘI A CERINȚELOR
DE PROIECT PENTRU REPARAȚIA PODULUI PESTE RÂUL RĂUT
ÎNTR-UN LOCALITĂȚILE USTIA ȘI ZOLONCENI DIN RAIONUL
CRIULENI**

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Podurile sunt obiecte din cadrul infrastructurii rutiere, construite prin lucrări tehnice pentru a susține o cale de comunicație și de a asigura continuitatea ei peste multiple obstacole, întâlnite în condițiile geografice ale traseului, obstacole pe care calea de comunicație le traversează modificând și unele elemente ale mediului. Obstacolele pot fi cursuri de apă, văi accidentate sau intersecții cu alte căi de comunicație, cum ar fi căile ferate sau chiar alte trasee rutiere. Prin urmare, podurile asigură continuitatea drumului peste obstacolul traversat, atât pe pod, iar în unele cazuri și sub acesta, datorită spațiului liber amenajat corespunzător cerințelor tehnice și rutiere.

În timpul lucrărilor de reparație a unor podurilor, care fac parte din procesul de reabilitare în zonele inundabile cum sunt văile râurilor, sunt utilizate echipamente grele și o varietate de utilaje, care produc modificări în albia minoră și cea majoră. La fel are loc degradarea vegetației locale, deteriorează structura solului, respectiv influențează negativ asupra ihtiofaunei din râu și a ecosistemelor adiacente. Ploile care cad în timpul acestor lucrări de construcție sau reparație, pot cauza formarea de jgheaburi de eroziune, pot deforma și afecta stabilitatea malurilor din văile râurilor, pot deplasa anumite cantități de materiale în albia râului care vor spori procesul de colmatare etc. Efectele lucrărilor menționate asupra zonelor inundabile sunt considerate semnificative și necesită implementarea unor măsuri de atenuare nemijlocit în timpul de realizare a proiectelor de reabilitare a drumurilor și a podurilor.

Rețeaua de drumuri din Republica Moldova depășește prin obiective de infrastructură precum podurile, multiple obstacole, în special râuri de diferite dimensiuni, iar rețeaua de râuri din bazinul Răutului nu este o excepție. Acest articol reflectă rezultatele cercetării condițiilor geografice în care a fost construit, apoi reabilitat podul peste râul Răut, amplasat între localitățile Ustia și Zolonceni din raionul Criuleni. Mărimea segmentului de râu în conformitate cu sistemului de ierarhizare a rețelelor de râuri după Horton-Strahler, peste care traversează acest pod este de ordinul VII, fiind cel mai mare în acest caz. Prin urmare, la realizarea proiectului s-a ținut prioritar cont de caracteristicile climatice, ale reliefului, cele geotehnice și hidrogeologice. În același timp, reparația podului și a traseului de drum din apropiere a vizat și un șir de măsuri de protecție a mediului, precum: minimizarea impactului asupra reliefului din valea râului, realizarea unor lucrări antierozionale, care să diminueze posibilitatea scurgerii materialului solid în râu, protecția vegetației și semănatul de vegetație ierboasă pentru consolidarea malurilor și a terenului adiacent carosabilului etc.

Key words: infrastructura rutieră, condițiile geografice ale traseului, rețeaua de râuri, cerințelor de proiect pentru reparația podului.

ADVANTAGES OF CRYOCONSERVATION OF SPERM IN REPRODUCTIVE BIOTECHNOLOGY

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Cryopreservation of sperm is one of the most important procedures in the development of biotechnologies for assisted reproduction. In some farm animals, the use of cryopreserved semen has multiple benefits. Cryopreservation of sperm allows long-term storage, dispersal of genes of genetically superior animals from one generation to another and long-distance transport of semen. Another advantage of using cryopreserved semen is that it facilitates the easy sowing of females at the optimal time of reproduction. Moreover, cryopreservation of sperm is an essential biotechnology for the management of sperm banks, thus contributing to the conservation of animal biodiversity and the protection of rare and endangered species. In scientific research, the main attention in this field has been paid to the improvement of biotechnologies and freezing-thawing regimes of semen in animal species of agricultural interest. The scientific interest consists in the use of antioxidants, cryoprotectants in optimal concentrations and minimizing the freezing-thawing time, which are some of the essential requirements in maintaining the structure and function of sperm during cryopreservation. The latter are very vulnerable in the freezing and thawing process, because the reproductive cells are very sensitive to thermal changes and their viability is compromised after thawing. Currently, neither the major achievements of scientific research on the synthesis of synthetic media and freezing protocols, the properties of the researched antioxidants, elucidating how low temperatures cause damage to sperm and a number of other factors do not fully solve the problem of sperm quality. The main damage that occurs during cryopreservation results from the exposure of reproductive cells to temperature variations, which leads to the formation of ice crystals, which structurally damage the inside of the cell and the environment. In parallel, osmotic changes occur. In addition, during freezing and thawing, irreversible lipid-protein changes occur in the plasma membrane as the primary structure of sperm. Thermal variations also change the configuration of phospholipids that increase the rigidity and fragility of the plasmalemma, as well as its permeability, causing a decrease in sperm metabolism. The cryopreservation process also causes chromatin damage that results in DNA fragmentation, the integrity of which varies with protamine, histone, and the intact disulfide bridges between cysteine residues. The effects of molecule damage during cryopreservation are directly reflected on the fertilizing capacity of frozen-thawed sperm. Thus, cryopreservation of sperm is an essential biotechnology of assisted reproduction in virtually all species of mammals, including humans.

Key words: cryopreservation of sperm, reproductive biotechnology, sperm banks, freezing-thawing regimes, sperm quality.

VIABILITY AND STABILITY OF AQUATIC FUNGI OF BIOTECHNOLOGICAL INTEREST AFTER LYOPHILIZATION

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Microorganisms are inexhaustible and advantageous sources of bioactive substances (antibiotics, vitamins, proteins, food additives, enzymes, organic acids, biopreparations for agricultural use, etc.), for which they are widely used in biotechnology. The sustainable functioning of national collections of microorganisms and their permanent completion is a key necessity for the further expansion of biotechnologies in all industrially developed countries. Fungi are a permanent component of aquatic ecosystems and belong to important microbial communities for organic decomposition, nutrient cycle and energy flows. Of particular interest are the obligatory aquatic species, i.e. those that not only appear and develop actively in water, but, most importantly, cannot reproduce outside the aquatic environment, but are also migratory fungi. Ecological groups found in the seas and freshwater include terrestrial fungi. According to data from various scientific publications, in freshwater environments, the most commonly detected are fungi representing the species: *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Trichoderma*, *Talaromyces*, *Acremonium*, *Alternaria*, *Fusarium*, *Mucor*, *Rhizopus*. Aquatic fungi produce hydrolytic enzymes that degrade many compounds, thus contributing to the purification of aquatic environments. In addition, they have a high metabolic capacity for carbon sequestration and are believed to be key elements in the carbon cycle and regulators of the global climate. The method of storage of microorganisms of industrial interest is important for any microbiological investigation, and their long-term conservation, without obvious modification of morphological-cultural and biochemical characters is a task of major importance for any collection. The aim of the research was to evaluate the viability and stability of aquatic fungi of biotechnological interest after lyophilization. The object of study was served 20 strains of aquatic fungi, isolated from the lake La izvor, which possesses significant enzymatic and antimicrobial activity. The strains were lyophilized in the defatted milk + 7% glucose protection medium. After lyophilization, the viability, enzymatic activity (catalase), and antifungal activity against phytopathogens were evaluated: *A. niger*, *Alt. Alternata*, *B. cinerea*, *F. solani*, *F. oxysporum*. The results obtained in the researches showed that the viability of aquatic fungal strains after lyophilization varies within the limits of 92.8-99%, compared to the initial titer, up to lyophilization. The antifungal activity of the strains, compared to phytopathogenic fungi, after lyophilization was approximately at the level up to lyophilization. Enzymatic activity (catalase) did not change significantly after lyophilization. Also, after lyophilization no changes of morphological and cultural peculiarities were detected. Thus, we can conclude that, after the lyophilization process, the studied fungal strains have kept their high viability and morphological, cultural and biosynthetic stability.

Acknowledgments: The research was funded out within the project 20.80009.7007.09 (ANCD).

Key words: collections of microorganisms, obligatory aquatic species, viability and stability of aquatic fungi, lyophilization, biosynthetic stability.

THE IMPACT OF ZnO AND Cu NANOPARTICLES SUPPLEMENTED IN THE REHYDRATION MEDIUM ON LYOPHILIZED MICROMYCETES

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Rehydration of lyophilized microorganisms is an important step in the recovery of strains from the state of anabiosis. There is a wide range of lyophilized strain regeneration media, which demonstrate various results. It has been shown experimentally that viability increases if the rehydration solution with the protective medium is selected correctly. When recovering cells after lyophilization, the duration and temperature of rehydration are important. Complex rehydration media play an important role in repairing damaged cells by providing additional nutrients and essential cell components. The rehydration process includes three simultaneous processes: absorbing water into the dry material, swelling and restoring the soluble materials in the cell. The extent of rehydration depends on the degree of damage to the cell structure and the chemical changes caused by dehydration.

At present, nanoparticles (NPs) are widely used in biotechnology and microbiology, with the help of which the biosynthetic processes of microorganisms used as producers of bioactive substances can be regulated. NPs, due to their very small size, are able to penetrate the body's microstructure, accumulate on the cell surface or penetrate the cell wall, thus altering the functioning of biological systems. Publications in recent years demonstrate the effect of NPs on the viability, development and biosynthetic processes in microorganisms. With the help of NPs introduced into the culture medium of microorganisms, their morphological features can be modified and biosynthetic processes can be stimulated, thus obtaining the expected microbial product of a higher quantity and quality.

The aim of the research was to study the impact of Cu and ZnO NPs supplemented in the rehydration medium on lyophilized micromycetes.

Twenty micromycete strains, representatives of the genera: *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, and *Trichoderma*. The strains were lyophilized in the defatted milk + 7% glucose protection medium. Rehydration of strains was performed with distilled H₂O - control variant and 2 NP variants (NP): H₂O + NP Cu; H₂O + NP ZnO. At the first stage, the optimal concentration of NP in the rehydration medium was selected. 3 concentrations (mg / l) were tested: 0.005; 0.001; 0.01.

The viability and stability of micromycete strains, after lyophilization, rehydrated with media supplemented with NP of Cu or ZnO in a concentration of 0.001 mg / l were evaluated. It was shown that in the variant with NP, the viability of the strains exceeds the control variant by 1-4%, and the antifungal activity of the strains of the genus *Penicillium* and *Trichoderma* significantly exceeds the control. In the variant with NP ZnO there was a decrease by 2-11% compared to the control.

Changes in the morpho-cultural properties of micromycete strains in the NP variants compared to the control variant were not detected.

Acknowledgments: The research was funded out within the project 20.80009.7007.09 (ANCD).

Key words: lyophilized micromycetes, rehydration medium, state of anabiosis, nanoparticles (NPs), culture medium of microorganisms.

**DENSITY DYNAMICS OF RODENT SPECIES IN AGROCENOSES IN THE
REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA IN 2021**

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Research carried out in the autumn wheat field at the "Horasti" station showed that at the beginning of the second decade of April the relative density was 5%. The dominant species is *A. sylvaticus* (100%). The females are lactating, they reproduce in the third decade of March. In the willow plantation along the dry canal, the density was 2.5%, the dominant species is *A. uralensis* (100%), males being developed. From now on, into the third decade of May, an upward dynamic in relative rodent density has been determined. The values of this parameter are as follows: grassy cover near the acacia grove – 11.5%; fallow bordered by the wheat field – 10.9% and the edge of the wheat field bordered by the willow plantation – 43.4%. As a result of favourable conditions, the wheat crop developed intensively and the spike was formed. In the fallow at the border with the wheat field the dominant species is *A. sylvaticus* (66.7%), which forms a community with *A. uralensis* (33.3%). The sex ratio for *A. sylvaticus* is 1:1, 50% of individuals being juveniles. This indicates a relatively strong reproductive potential. The highest relative density was recorded in the wheat field ecotone with the willow plantation (43.4%). An 8-fold increase in the relative density of rodent populations was recorded in the wheat field in the spring period concomitant with the upward trend in rainfall. In July, a relative rodent density of 26.7% was recorded in the wheat field ecotone with fallow. This crop is at the final ripening stage, but not yet harvested due to unfavourable weather conditions (heavy rainfall). Wheat dominates in the wheat field ecotone with fallow, with 33.3% of *M. spicilegus* species. Its presence was recorded only in July. It is followed by *A. sylvaticus*, *A. flavicollis* and *A. uralensis* with 16.7% each. The dominance of *M. arvalis* and *A. agrarius* is 8.3%. Following the harvest of the autumn wheat crop at the end of July, the relative density of small rodents decreased compared to the beginning of the month (15.8%). In September, the following relative density values were recorded: in the forest belt bordered by the plowland – 17.3%, in the forest belt bordered by fallow – 11.8% and in the ecotone of acacia forest bordered by the sunflower field – 21.4%. The decrease in relative density values compared to the previous months is explained by the reduced amount of precipitation during this period, which is reflected by the lower aridity index (25). The small rodent community in the forest fallow biotope consists of three species, the dominant being *A. flavicollis* (50%). *A. agrarius* and *M. arvalis* are dominant with 25% each. At the end of October, the relative density of rodents in the forest strip was 6.7%, the ecotone of the forest strip with fallow and the ecotone of the unharvested maize field bordered by the forest strip along the dry canal – 20% each. In the poplar field the dominance of *M. arvalis* was 66.7%, followed by *A. agrarius*, *A. flavicollis*, *A. sylvaticus* with 11.1% each.

Key words: rodent species, density dynamics, reproductive potential, relative density, dominant species.

COMPLEX APPLICATION OF *BACILLUS SPP.* AND BIOREGULATORS FOR THE CONTROL OF PESTS

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The losses to the world agriculture, various crops and agricultural products caused by diseases, weeds and pests, account for 35% of the annual production. An increase in yield per hectare can be obtained through the use of scientifically based protection systems. On a global scale, microbial pesticides only account for approximately 1–2% of all pesticides sold; however, they have shown long term growth over the past decade in contrast to chemical pesticides, which have consistently declined in the global market (Bailey et al., 2010). Some sources have recently estimated that the growth in microbial pesticides could reach 3% of the pesticide market in 2014 (Glare et al., 2012). The development and use of bacterial biopesticides as classical, conservation and augmentative biological control agents have included a number of successes and some setbacks in the past 15 years.

The aim of the work was to establish the possibility of entomopathogenic strains *Bacillus thuringiensis* ssp. *kurstaki* (Bt) and *Bacillus thuringiensis* ssp. *thuringiensis* (BT) application in a tank mixture for spraying. For this purpose, the effect of the recommended and half concentrations of para-aminobenzoic acid (PABA) on the above mentioned bacteria colonies was examined *in vitro*. Bacteria were cultivated in liquid mineral nutrient medium for 48 hours at 29°C to the titer of 10⁹ CFU/ml. The suspension was inoculated on the agarized CGA nutrient media in Petri dishes. After bacterial cultures had grown for 24 hours, sterile disks (five disks per three Petri dishes) soaked in the substance biologic active emulsions were placed on their surfaces. After a week of incubation, the interaction of the studied concentrations of para-aminobenzoic acid (PABA) with bacterial culture was recorded. Bacterial growth inhibition zones were not found. This allows to assume that it is possible to combine working solutions of bioregulators with bacterial strains suspensions and at the same time to reduce the para-aminobenzoic acid (PABA) after effect. The similar results have been reported for *B. thuringiensis* mixtures with the pesticides Sumi-Alpha, Regent, Decis and *Pseudomonas* sp. *Bacillus* sp. with the pesticides Ridomil, Quadris, Raxil and Colfo-Super (Адрианов Ф.Д., 2011; Попов Ю.Б., 2008; Войтка Д.В., 2018).

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Key words: *Bacillus* spp., bioregulators, bacterial biopesticides, para-aminobenzoic acid.

IMPACT OF NANOPARTICLES IN THE CULTIVATION MEDIUM ON THE VIABILITY AND STABILITY OF MICROMYCETES AFTER LYOPHILIZATION

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One of the factors influencing the viability of micromycetes after lyophilization and prolonged storage is the cultivation medium used before. Cultivation media are substrates that provide the nutrients and physico-chemical conditions necessary for the growth and multiplication of microorganisms. The nutritional needs of microorganisms for optimal growth and development are individual and this must be taken into account when preparing cultivation media. The main factors that ensure the vital activity, growth, and reproduction of microorganisms are nutrition, respiration and living conditions. Currently, nanoparticles (NP) are a means of stimulating the growth and biosynthetic processes of micromycetes of biotechnological interest. Research on the effect of NP on biological objects is necessary and current, because NP are obtained through nanotechnologies from modified materials at the atomic or molecular level. They have unique properties, with a different behavior from conventional materials. The action of NP on microorganisms, according to data from the literature, is different and depends on the microorganism studied, the quantity, size, and duration of the applied NP. NP can stimulate the growth and development of microorganisms, but also decrease or inhibit their growth. The aim of the research: to study the impact of supplemented NP in the culture medium on the viability and stability of micromycetes after lyophilization. In the study were taken 20 strains of micromycetes from the genera *Aspergillus* (5), *Penicillium* (10), *Trichoderma* (5). The strains were grown on Czapek medium - the control variant, and variants in which Czapek medium was supplemented with NP: Cu, Co, ZnO, Fe₂O₃, Fe₂ZnO₄, Fe₂CuO₄, in different concentrations. It was found that the action of NP studied, on the morpho-cultural peculiarities is individual, the best cultures grow and develop on Czapek medium supplemented with NP of Fe₂ZnO₄, Fe₂CuO₄, ZnO, in a concentration of 5 mg / l. NP Fe₂CuO₄, Fe₂ZnO₄, ZnO, supplemented in the micromycete cultivation medium before lyophilization, acted differently on their viability. In some cases, they stimulated, and in other cases they decreased the viability of the strains after lyophilization. Thus, the evaluation of the viability of the strains after 1 year of lyophilized storage, showed that the decrease of the viability of the strains in the variants with NP during storage is slower compared to the control variant. In most cultures, after 1 year of lyophilized storage, the viability in NP variants exceeded the control by 2-10%. It has also been established that NP Fe₂ZnO₄, Fe₂CuO₄, ZnO substituted in the culture medium before lyophilization has a positive effect on the biosynthetic properties of micromycetes. NP Fe₂ZnO₄ and ZnO act more beneficial on the biosynthetic properties, stimulating the antifungal activity against the tested phytopathogens from 2.2% to 21.4%, compared to the control.

Acknowledgments: The research was funded out within the project 20.80009.7007.09 (ANCD).

Key words: nanoparticles, viability, stability, micromycetes, lyophilization.

**THE QUALITY OF FRESH AND ENSEILED BIOMASS FROM
NEW CULTIVAR „MARIA” OF *HELIANTHUS TUBEROSUS***

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Topinambur *Helianthus tuberosus* L. belonging to the botanical family Asteraceae, native to the central region of North America, is a crop with great potential for human consumption, generating tubers that store carbohydrates such as inulin and fructooligosaccharides have beneficial effects on nutrition and human health. The aerial part is used as fodder for animals in the summer season and the tubers in the winter season. *Helianthus tuberosus* is food resource for pollinators, since flowering occurs at a time of low food supply for bees and wasps.

The main objective of this research has been to evaluate quality of fresh and ensiled biomass from new cultivar „Maria” of topinambur, *Helianthus tuberosus* which has been cultivated in the experimental field of the National Botanical Garden (Institute), Chișinău, and prospects of its use as fodder for farm animals or as substrates for biomethane production. The results of our research revealed that the dry matter of the harvested whole plants contained 117 g/kg CP, 77 g/kg ash, 329 g/kg CF, 360 g/kg ADF, 586 g/kg NDF, 64 g/kg ADL, 296 g/kg Cel, 226 g/kg HC, 214 g/kg TSS, with nutritive value 60.9% DMD, RFV= 97, 12.03 MJ/kg DE, 9.88 MJ/kg ME and 5.89 MJ/kg NEI. The ensiled mass was characterized by agreeable colour with specific smell and pH 3.85, the silage dry matter contained 116 g/kg CP, 99 g/kg ash, 345 g/kg ADF, 522 g/kg NDF, 46 g/kg ADL, 299 g/kg Cel, 177 g/kg HC, 214 g/kg TSS, with nutritive value 62.0% DMD, RFV= 111, 12.24 MJ/kg DE, 9.91 MJ/kg ME and 6.06 MJ/kg NEI. The green and ensiled mass substrates for anaerobic digestion, have optimal C/N ratio, amount of lignin and hemicellulose, biomethane potential varied from 272 to 329 l/kg ODM.

The green mass and silage obtained from the new cultivar „Maria” of *Helianthus tuberosus* largely meets the standards and can be used as alternative feed for animals and substrate for anaerobic digestion in biogas plants.

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Key words: *Helianthus tuberosus*, quality of biomass, cultivar „Maria”, alternative feed, substrate for anaerobic digestion.

VALORIZATION OF WINE YEAST SEDIMENTS AS A SOURCE OF LIPID PREPARATIONS

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Currently, various types of medicinal, food and animal feed preparations are developed on the basis of biologically active compounds of microbial origin. It has been demonstrated that yeasts could be used as biotechnological object, due to the high quality of biomass, are an excellent source for valuable biological compounds, such as vitamins, amino acids, unsaturated fatty acids, polysaccharides, antioxidant enzymes and other metabolites.

According to the specialized literature, bioadditives obtained from microbial biomass, due to the safety and effectiveness, significantly increase productivity and fertility of farm animals. Particular attention is paid to the problem of using yeast sediments, rich in valuable biocomponents, which accumulated in significant quantities on wineries and can be used in agricultural and industrial activities.

Determination of the biochemical composition of yeast sediments such as a secondary product derived from the wine production process, is of great practical importance for development of the new preparations based on the biologically active compounds, in particular lipids.

Thus, the purpose of this research was to evaluate the biochemical composition of the yeast biomass obtained from wine waste sediments for obtaining of lipid preparations with the perspective for use in animal husbandry.

The yeast biomass after production of the *Merlot*, *Cabernet* and *Rkatsiteli* wines, offered by the Cricova winery, was used as research object. Lipid content in the biomass was determined gravimetrically by extraction with the mixture of ethanol:chloroform:acetic acid. Determination of the fractional composition of lipids was carried out by the method of thin layer chromatography.

In the study of total lipid content, it was established that the yeast biomass contained from 2.5 ± 0.03 by $11.1 \pm 1.0\%$ d. w. of lipids, the maximal lipids accumulation has been identified in sediments from the *Rkatsiteli* white wine. As a results of the lipid fractionation procedure, it was demonstrated that the yeast sediments is characterized by the content of phospholipids - $17.43 \pm 1.05 \dots 20.61 \pm 0.77\%$, sterols - $13.77 \pm 0.54 \dots 20.01 \pm 0.19\%$, diglycerides - $13.61 \pm 0.13 \dots 14.85 \pm 1.06\%$, triglycerides - $15.96 \pm 1.0 \dots 22.32 \pm 0.84\%$, sterol ethers - $26.35 \pm 0.77 \dots 40.23 \pm 2.39\%$ of the total amount of lipids.

Thus, according to the obtained data, we can conclude that the yeast biomass such as by-products of the wine industry can be used as an excellent source for the production of lipid preparations. The utilization of wastes from the wine industry contributes for the protection of environment.

Acknowledgments: The results were obtained within Project 20.80009.5107.16 New biologically active microbial preparations for increasing the reproductive and productive potential of animals of zootechnical interest, funded by the NARD.

Key words: lipid preparations, biochemical composition, yeast biomass, wine industry.

CAPACITY OF MICROBIAL MULTIPLICATION DEPENDING ON THE FORM OF PREPARATION OF SOME ONCOPROTECTIVE PLANTS

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The constant increase of oncological morbidity affects the condition of the normal intestinal microbial flora, presenting an aggravating element in the case of chemo- and radiotherapy. The quantitative decrease of bifido and lactobacteria leads to the onset of dysbiosis, which in turn causes various physiological disorders. Globally, there is a growing interest in the use of natural herbal remedies against many diseases of various etiologies. Some native medicinal plants were used in the study, which contain anticancer, antitumor and antiproliferative agents: celandine (*Chelidonium majus*); mistletoe (*Viscum album*); wormwood (*Artemisia absinthium*); thorns (*Xanthium spinosum*) and calamus (*Acorus calamus*). Selective culture medias based on decoction, infusion, alcoholic tincture and cold maceration, prepared from the medicinal plants mentioned above, on the degree of multiplication of some representatives of normal microbial flora were tested. Subsequently, two forms of preparation were selected for each medicinal plant, which proved to be more effective. The data obtained show a different multiplication of bifido- and lactobacteria depending on the pharmaceutical form of preparation: celandine in the form of decoction led to an increase of 5.21 and 9.06%, compared to the tincture; cold macerated mistletoe - by 8.04 and 4.12%, compared to the infusion of this plant; wormwood infusion showed a better performance by 7.20 and 12.35% compared to tincture; thorns in the form of cold maceration - by 2.42 and 1.59%, compared to the infusion; and regarding calamus, no substantial difference was found between the form of cold maceration and infusion (powder preparations), compared to the decoction, for the preparation of which the dried plant was used. Cold maceration of mistletoe and thorns is more effective compared to other forms of preparation, probably due to mucilage, which contains both common plants with other substances – free amino acids, viscous acid, polysaccharides, glycosides, everectin, minerals, vitamin C, choline, acetylcholine.

Thus, the cold macerated form proved to be the most effective in the case of two medicinal plants – mistletoe and thorn; the form of alcohol-based tincture had less influence on the multiplication of lactobacteria compared to bifidobacteria (wormwood and celandine). The infusion form can be used in subsequent research for wormwood, and calamus – in any form of preparation. When developing microbial phytopreparations with oncoprotective action, it is necessary to consider the potential anticancer, the dose and the optimal pharmaceutical form of preparation of medicinal plants, their impact on the intestinal microbial flora, as well as the risks. Being adjuvant preparations and less toxic than traditional therapies, they can still interact with some drugs (celandine may increase or decrease the effect of some drugs, wormwood may reduce the effectiveness of anticonvulsants, calamus may interact with anticoagulants, sedatives), so care is needed.

Key words: *Chelidonium majus, Viscum album, Artemisia absinthium, Xanthium spinosum, Acorus calamus* adjuvant preparations, oncoprotective plants.

**NEW FAUNISTIC RECORDS OF THE ENDANGERED SPECIES
PROSERPINUS PROSERPINA (LEPIDOPTERA: SPHINGIDAE) FROM
THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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The Hawk-moths (Lepidoptera: Sphingidae) are among the largest and most easily recognized Lepidoptera. Hawk-moths are medium-sized to large moths with strong and robust bodies and relatively short wings. Most species are nocturnal, but some genera (e.g. *Hemaris*) are active during the day.

In the fauna of the Republic of Moldova the family Sphingidae is represented by 20 species, about 53% of the European fauna. Four species from this family require protection and conservation: *Acherontia atropos*, *Dolbina elegans*, *Marumba quercus* and *Proserpinus proserpina*. The species *Proserpinus proserpina* are mentioned in the Red Book of the Republic of Moldova (2015) with critically endangered statut (CR). The species is also included in the Bern Convention (Annex II), IUCN Red List of Threatened Animals in Category VU and Nature 2000. *Proserpinus proserpina*, are cited in the Red Book of Ukraine with CR statut, and the Red List of Romania with VU statut.

The species are mentioned for the first time in the fauna of the Republic of Moldova in 1929 by Miller E., Zubovschi N. and Ruscinschi A. in the “*Bulletin of the National Museum of Natural History*”, being so far the only reporting on the territory of the country. The authors mentioned that found a larvae of this species near the village of Bularda (Călărași district).

Following research conducted in 2012-2021, the species has been reported only in Horăști village (Ialoveni district), on 02.05.22, leg. Galina Bușmachiu.

Fig. The species *Proserpinus proserpina*, Horăști (Ialoveni district), 02.05.22
(Photo: Galina Bușmachiu)

The species develops one generation. Adults take flight in May-June. Butterflies are active at dusk and night, feed on the nectar of flowers attracted by their strong smell, such as *Jasminus* and *Echium*. Larve develop from July to August-September. The caterpillars generally feed on *Epilobium*, but rarely on the eponymous *Oenothera*. Hibernates in pupal stage in the soil. *Proserpinus proserpina* inhabits moist, warm habitats such as wetlands, gravel pits, meadow ditches, stream banks and clearcuts. The limitation factors are the distruction of natural habitats (drainage and intensification).

Acknowledgments: The researches were carried in the project 20.80009.7007.02. from State program of the Institute of Zoology.

Key words: *Proserpinus proserpina*, endangered species, red book, fauna, conservation.

DYNAMICS OF ACCUMULATION OF EXOPOLYSACCHARIDES IN CULTURAL LIQUID AT THE CULTIVATION OF *SPIRULINA PLATENSIS* SUPPLEMENTED WITH COORDINATIVE COMPOUNDS OF CU (II)

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Spirulina platensis is considered an excellent source of protein, vitamins, lipids, minerals, polysaccharides, nucleic acids, enzymes and pigments. In recent years, many polysaccharides isolated from seaweed have found applications in food, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics. Polysaccharides are a type of biomacromolecules that exist as structural components of the cell wall of seaweed and possess such activities as anti-tumour, immunomodulatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, anticoagulant, antiviral etc. Usually, the bioactivities of polysaccharides are closely correlated with their chemical properties, such as molecular dimensions, types and ratios of constitutive monosaccharides and the characteristics of glycosidic bonds.

In this context, the aim of the present research was to evaluate the dynamics of accumulation of exopolysaccharides in the cultural liquid of the cyanobacterium *Sp. platensis* at the cultivation on the mineral nutrient *SP-1* supplemented with coordinative compounds of Cu (II), depending some parameters and cultivation conditions (temperature, pH and irradiation regime). Productivity of *Sp. platensis* was determined daily using photocolometric methods. As a stimulator and regulator of EPS synthesis, was selected the coordinative compound $[\text{CuL}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ in a concentration of 2 mg / l which had a maximum effect on their synthesis, when spirulina was cultured for 7 days. Cultivation was performed for 26 days, during which time the acidic and sulfated exopolysaccharides content was recorded on each cultivation day. Thus, it was attested that there is a gradual accumulation of acidic exopolysaccharides, the maximum accumulation of was detected on the 18th day, reaching the value of 55.08 mg / l, then there is a gradual decrease in their content. In the case of the reference sample, the content of exopolysaccharides accumulated up to day 18 shows lower values than in the case of the compound $\text{CuL}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, but their content continues to increase, reaching a maximum of 63.83 mg/l on 22nd day, in the following days the exopolysaccharide content decreases insignificantly. The dynamics of the accumulation of sulfated exopolysaccharides in the cultural liquid of spirulina shows like in the case of acidic exopolysaccharides, the maximum value on the 18th day being about 46.00 mg/l approximately 85% of total accumulated EPS After the 18th day of cultivation, the sulfated EPS content gradually decreases, so on the 26th day the values stabilize at 33.91 mg / l. As a result of this research we can deduce the following conclusion that under the action of the coordinative compound $\text{CuL}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ the maximum accumulation of total acidic and sulfated exopolysaccharides is recorded earlier (day 18) than in the case of the reference sample (day 22) and the presence of Cu^{2+} ions, influenced the synthesis and accumulation of acidic and sulfated exopolysaccharides in the cultural liquid of the cyanobacterium *Spirulina platensis*.

Key words: *Spirulina platensis*, exopolysaccharides, cultural liquid, coordinative compound, dynamics of the accumulation.

**METHODS OF CONSERVATION OF MICROALGAE
AND CYANOBACTERIA**

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Microorganisms are one of the most essential components of the biosphere. The creation and maintenance of a collection of microorganisms plays an extremely important role in the study of microbial diversity, as well as in the conservation of genetically stable producers used in biotechnological production, medicine and environmental biotechnology. Of the 50,000 species of microalgae, it is estimated that about 2.5% are found in culture collections. The development of methods for the conservation of cyanobacteria and microalgae is less intensive than for other groups of microorganisms. Conservation methods can be divided into two groups: periodic cultivation and long-term conservation methods. Periodic cultivation of cyanobacterial and microalgae cultures is used to maintain healthy, physiologically, morphologically and genetically representative specimens. It is attractive to researchers due to its simplicity, the constant availability of crops for work and the ability to control their purity and properties. The needs to maintain the genetic stability of the species, the high costs and the laborious re-sowing of algae have led to the development of methods for their long-term conservation, which have different efficiencies.

The freeze-drying method is a method of storing dry cells, which allows them to be stored for a long time at low temperatures, usually at 4 ° C, without access to oxygen, humidity and light. Lyophilization does not ensure 100% preservation of the viability of microorganism cells and the highest quality of a dry product. It leads to the selection of the most resistant cells in culture, which may not have the desired properties. This method is used successfully to preserve cyanobacteria that reproduce by akinetes (spores), as well as for those species that are able to synthesize exopolysaccharides. Freeze-drying for many algae ensures extremely low levels of crop viability (0-1%) during storage and is not suitable for long-term storage. Therefore, lyophilization is an effective preservation method only for some algae strains. Suspension of cells with protective agents before lyophilization (skim milk, sucrose) increases the number of surviving cultures. Cryopreservation methods are performed by direct immersion of ampoules with microorganisms and cryoprotective solution in liquid nitrogen at -196 °C Cryoprotectants increase the viability of cells at cryogenic temperatures. The most commonly used cryoprotective compounds are dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), glycerol and methanol.

Thus, the issue of long-term conservation of microalgae is relevant, current and attractive to researchers and is one of the basic objectives of the national collection of non-pathogenic microorganisms that constantly seeks to improve conservation methods for long-term storage of microalgae and other microbial resources valuable.

Acknowledgments: The research was funded out within the project 20.80009.7007.09 (ANCD).

Key words: conservation, microalgae, cyanobacteria, national collection, long-term storage, microbial resources.

ACTINOBACTERIA AS BIOCONTROL AGENTS FOR COMBATING PEST INSECTS

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In the pursuit of profit and food security, in the condition of climate change, world agriculture, applying excessive various synthetic inputs, provoke many negative phenomena, which seriously affect human health and the state of the environment. Since the application of pesticide against pests and different hazardous to environment and human health, many efforts have been oriented in order to elaboration and application of ecologic friendly means.

To ensure the sustainable development of agriculture, many novel products have been discovered from the research and development on biological plant protection, which are superior in safety for humans and environmental. Among the microbiological means of plant protection, a special place belongs to actinobacteria, which are prevalent in soil, water, crops and environment. Thus, actinobacteria became as a good alternative for the management of crop pests. These, as well as the metabolites found in actinobacteria, serve to develop a significant range of effective and harmless preparations.

The avermectins, represents a group of macrocyclic lactones natural means homologues produced by the soil *Streptomyces avermitilis* and act as a complex of eight closely related avermectins, which demonstrate the highly pathogenic to many arthropods. Abamectin is considered as a selective pesticide, which has several advantageous traits include safe to humans and environment and low pathogeny to nontarget pests. Emamectin benzoate is a synthetic version of abamectin having broader insecticidal activity than abamectin. Milbemectin is an insecticidal and acaricidal product isolated from the fermentation broth of *Streptomyces hygroscopicus*, which are the secondary metabolites of actinobacteria. The polynactins are very effective against mites under high moisture conditions and have been utilized for the management of thus pests.

The spinosyns are a distinctive family of fermentation-derived insecticides, from *Saccharopolyspora spinosa* having potent activity against a large spectrum of insects and have lower environmental impact.

Our research is aimed at determining the morphological and cultural characteristics, the possibility of growing on various culture media, as well as the activity in the control of harmful insects, which cannot be effectively combated with other environmentally harmless means of protection.

Acknowledgments: The work was carried out with the support of the State Program project (2020-2023) „The synergism between natural factors and microbiological, environmentally friendly, means of regulating of the population’s density of harmful organisms for the crops protection in conventional and organic farming” no. 20.80009.7007.16.

Key words: actinobacteria, biocontrol agents, pest insects, biological plant protection, avermectins.

**HELMINTOFAUNA IN PHEASANT (*PHASIANUS COLCHICUS L.*)
MAINTAINED IN CAPTIVITY IN MOLDOVA**

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The common pheasant (*Phasianus colchicus L.*) is the most important bird for the avian fauna of the Republic of Moldova, both in terms of numbers and distribution, as well as hunting perspectives.

The efficient and continuous exploitation of species for hunting purposes requires the most detailed knowledge of their way of life, the correlations between the populations of this species, as well as their level of parasite infestation (Zamornea M. et al. 2017).

The investigations regarding the determination of the pheasant parasite species have been performed in the Parasitology and Helminthology Laboratory of the Institute of Zoology. Biological, samples were collected from the Central area of the Republic of Moldova in the period 2020-2022.

The following methods were used: the coproovoscopic methods (Fulleborn, Darling), the coprolarvoscopic methods (Popov, Baermann), partial parasitological investigations (after K. I. Skriabin) and successive washing were used. The collected material was further examined using the MFC-9 magnifier (ob.14x2) and the Novex Holland B ob microscope. 20-40 WF 10x Din / 20mm.

In pheasants from the 127 samples collected, 14 parasite species were recorded: *Capillaria annulata* (Molin, 1858), *Syngamus tracheia* (Montagu, 1811), *Heterakis isolonche* (Linstow, 1906), *Ascaridia galli* (Schränk, 1788), *Heterakis gallinarum* (Schränk, 1788), *Trichostrongylus tenuis* (Mehlis, 1846), *Capillaria caudinflata* (Zeder, 1800), *Eimeria colchici* (Norton, 1967), *Eimeria duodenalis* (Norton, 1967), *Eimeria phasiani* (Tyzzer, 1929), *Choanotaenia infundibulum* (Bloch, 1779), *Raillietina tetragona* (Molin, 1858), *Prosthogonimus ovatus* (Rud., 1803), *Raillietina echinobotrida* (Megnin, 1880), which were distributed in the 4 classes (*Trematoda*, *Cestoda*, *Nematoda*, *Conoidasida*), 7 families (*Prosthogonimidae*, *Davaineidae*, *Capillariidae*, *Syngamidae*, *Heterakidae*, *Trichostrongylidae*, *Emeriidae*) and 8 genera (*Prosthogonimus*, *Raillietina*, *Capillaria*, *Syngamus*, *Heterakis*, *Ascaridia*, *Trichostrongylus*, *Eimeria*).

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Key words: *Phasianus colchicus L.*, helminthofauna, avian fauna, parasite infestation.

**PRODUCTIVITY, CAROTENOID AND GLYCEROL CONTENT OF
DUNALIELLA SALINA CULTIVATED IN THE PRESENCE OF GeO_2 WITH
VARYING LIGHTING REGIME**

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Due to the increased content of bioactive substances, especially carotenoids and glycerol, microalga *Dunaliella salina* is of interest and practical advantage in industrial cultivation, being a microalga of biotechnological interest. And due to the metabolisation by *D. salina* of microelements from the structure of chemical compounds, microalgal biomass acquires high nutritional values and new qualitative properties (immunostimulatory, regeneratory, cytoprotective etc.), a valuable fact in obtaining ecological multifunctional products with unique properties.

The trends of modern biotechnology require obtaining products in a closed cycle by reusing industrial waste. Green microalga *D. salina* is also an attractive object for the cultivation on the liquid waste especially obtained from the production of the biomass of other microalgae. Thus, the aim of this research was to evaluate the productivity, the content of carotenoids and glycerol in the biomass of *D. salina* cultivated on organo-mineral medium, elaborated from the cultural liquid, resulting from the cultivation of *Spirulina platensis* (production waste), in the presence of GeO_2 compound with the modification of lighting.

It was established that light intensity is an important factor in the accumulation of *D. salina* biomass, cultivated both in the absence and in the presence of the GeO_2 compound. The productivity of the control sample grown under intense illumination was 54.2% higher than the control sample grown under regular illumination. The addition of the GeO_2 inorganic compound showed an increase in the *D. salina* productivity by 12.4% at the concentration of 10 mg/L compound and regular lighting, and by 11.2% at the concentration of 20 mg/L, but intense lighting, compared to corresponding control samples.

In the samples grown under regular illumination (3500 lx), the most representative stimulating effect on the synthesis of carotenoids was observed for 5 mg/L GeO_2 compound. The content of carotenoids increased with 22.95%. The further increase of the GeO_2 concentration led to the decrease of the carotenoid content. In the samples grown under intense illumination (5000 lx), the highest content of carotenoids were obtained at the addition of the maximal concentration of GeO_2 (20 mg/L). The increase of the carotenoid content was 27%.

The amount of glycerol increased with the increase of the GeO_2 concentration in the samples cultivated under intense illumination (5000 lx) and showed the highest experimental values at the maximal added concentration of 20 mg/L. The increase of glycerol was 33.2%, compared to the control sample. At the regular illumination (3500 lx), only the addition of the minimal concentration of the GeO_2 compound (5 mg/L) stimulated the synthesis of the glycerol. The increase of glycerol content was 24.2%, compared to the control sample. As the concentration of GeO_2 increased in the culture medium, the accumulation of glycerol in the *D. salina* biomass decreased.

Key words: *Dunaliella salina*, productivity, content of carotenoids, glycerol, biotechnology.

ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF POLYSACCHARIDE-CONTAINING SPIRULINA EXTRACTS

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In recent years, the research on cyanobacteria and algae has demonstrated that many extracts obtained from their biomass have been shown to have antibacterials, antivirals, antioxidantes, antitumoral effects.

Cyanobacterium *Spirulina platensis* is widely used as food bioadditives due to its valuable biochemical composition: high protein content (60–70%), including phycobiliproteins, acid polysaccharides, polyunsaturated fatty acids, β -carotene, chlorophyll a, vitamins, minerals, and the presence of secondary metabolites such as polyphenols, sterols, et.al

For the qualitative screening of the antimicrobial activity of the investigated polysaccharides extracts, the well method was used, standardized for the control of the antimicrobial activity proposed by the CLSI standard.

The extract with polysaccharides content obtained from the biomass of spirulina cultivated in the presence of the zinc acetate showed bactericidal action on the strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC25923 and *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 11778 in 1: 1 dilution and inhibitory action in 1: 2 dilution.

The extract with polysaccharide content obtained from standard biomass showed bactericidal action in 1:1 dilution and inhibitory action in dilution of 1:2 on *S. aureus* ATCC25923 strains and only inhibitory action in 1: 2 dilution on *B. cereus* ATCC 11778 strains.

In the future, the action of polysaccharide-containing spirulina extracts on some gram-negative bacteria will be researched, as well as their antifungal action.

Key words: *Spirulina platensis*, polysaccharides, bactericidal action, antimicrobial activity.